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Optimizing H.265 Real-Time Streaming

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Abstract

In this thesis, we tried to optimize the current State-of-the-Art H.265 live streaming especially for panoramic video captures. The idea was to utilize the tiling technique used in the H.265 codec, which allows the video to be divided into independent regions. By transmitting only the currently seen part of the panoramic video in high quality, and reducing the quality the further away the Tiles are from the current viewport, we can reduce the bandwidth requirements while still maintaining a seamless, low latency, high-quality live experience.

To realize this, we set up a server environment that is capable of receiving a H.265 encoded panoramic live video stream, which is then converted into multiple quality levels while splitting the entire panoramic video into individual regions, which can be downloaded separately. To obtain those tiles in downloadable format, we utilized the DASH protocol, which is capable of creating a media presentation description file that includes all the information about the position, time, and quality level of each tile and can be interpreted by a client.

For the client side, we decided to use the Unity Engine to create an Android application which can be run on VR devices as well as smartphones. There we implemented a tile selection method that can divide the tiles into four different groups depending on their position relative to the current view of the user. With that information, we download the correct files from the server and recreate a playable video containing multiple quality-level tiles, which drastically reduces the network requirements. In addition, we implemented a custom video player using the native Android Media library to ensure seamless video playback without stutter or delay and provide the user with the best possible viewing experience.

Kurzfassung

In dieser Arbeit haben wir versucht, den aktuellen Stand der Technik im Bereich des H.265 Livestreaming für Panorama Videoaufnahmen zu optimieren. Die Grundidee bestand darin, die enthaltene Tiling Technik des H.265 Codec zu nutzen, die es ermöglicht das Video in unabhängige Regionen zu unterteilen. Durch die Übertragung der Bildbereiche in hoher Qualität, welche sich im Sichtfeld des Benutzers befinden, und die Reduzierung der Qualität, desto weiter die einzelnen Bildbereiche vom Sichtfeld entfernt sind, lassen sich die Netzwerk Anforderungen verringern, während gleichzeitig ein nahtloses, latenzfreies, hoch qualitatives Live Erlebnis gewährleistet wird.

Um dies umzusetzen, haben wir eine Serverumgebung eingerichtet, welche in der Lage ist, einen H.265 kodierten Panorama Livestream zu empfangen. Dieser wird dann in mehreren Qualitätsstufen konvertiert, während das ganze Bild in unabhängige Regionen unterteilt wird, die separat heruntergeladen werden können. Um diese in einem geeigneten Format bereitstellen zu können, haben wir das DASH-Protokoll eingesetzt, welches eine Media Presentation Description Datei erstellt, die sämtliche Informationen über Position, Zeit, und Qualitätsstufe der einzelnen Bildbereiche enthält und von einem Endgerät interpretiert werden kann.

Für die Client Seite haben wir uns entschieden die Unity Engine zu verwenden, um eine Android Anwendung zu entwickeln welche auf VR Geräten als auch auf Smartphones ausgeführt werden kann. Dort implementierten wir eine Tile Auswahl, die anhand der relativen Position zur derzeitigen Blickrichtung, die Tiles in vier Kategorien unterteilt. Mit dieser Information werden die passenden Dateien vom Server geladen und zu einem funktionierendem vollständigen Panoramavideo zusammengesetzt, bestehend aus verschiedenen Qualitätsstufen, was die Netzwerkanforderungen stark reduziert. Zusätzlich haben wir mithilfe der Android Media Bibliothek einen maßgeschneiderten Videoplayer entwickelt, welcher eine unterbrechungsfreie Wiedergabe ohne Ruckeln und Verzögerungen ermöglicht, um dem Endbenutzer das bestmögliche Erlebnis zu bieten.

Affidavit

I declare that I have authored this thesis independently, that I have not used other than the declared sources/resources, and that I have explicitly indicated all material which has been quoted either literally or by content from the sources used.

The text document uploaded to TUGRAZonline is identical to the present master's thesis dissertation.

16.09.2025

Date

Signature

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Nowadays digital videos are present in all daily lives, present in entertainment, communication, education, and many other fields. As video content consumption continues to grow across different kind of devices and platforms, the efficient transmission of video data is becoming a more important topic. This process includes multiple complex technologies, starting from the capture of the raw video signal, followed by compression into a usable format that retains all important visual information while still reducing the amount of data, which can then be transmitted to certain receiving devices over networks with different bandwidth constraints. Finally, a receiving device needs to be capable of decompressing the data to playback the obtained video on the devices display in such a way that the user gets a visually pleasing experience. Therefore, each stage of this pipeline needs to be optimized to ensure high quality videos without delays, stutter, or visual artifacts.

To address the diversity of video applications, a wide range of video compression and streaming techniques were developed. For example, live video streaming requires low-latency transmission and real-time encoding, while with Video On Demand (VOD) compression efficiency and buffering strategies are of much higher importance. Another example would be video conferences, where it is important that there is a consistent frame rate and low bitrates, as well as no stutter and delay, to have interactive communication. Each of these use cases has their own requirements and trade-offs, which are addressed by multiple different techniques such as encoding strategies, network protocols, quality control mechanisms, and many more.

In addition, a growing topic in video streaming is the personalized view of the captured and provided video for each individual user. In this case there are mostly panoramic videos where the user can decide which region is of interest, using a phone, a PC or a Virtual-Reality (VR) headset. This interactive and user-driven viewing experience brings completely new approaches to optimize the video transmission pipeline to users. Since they typically only focus on a limited portion of the panoramic scene at any given time, it is inefficient to transmit the entire video at full resolution. By using this knowledge that only a small portion of the whole video will actually be seen, and even a smaller portion

is in the focal area of the human visual field, methods for reducing the video quality in regions which are not directly seen and not in the focal area were introduced. This does not only lead to a reduction of bandwidth requirements for video streaming but also to a reduction of the rendering effort on the clients' device.

This is the point where we want to contribute to ongoing research by proposing an approach for the efficient compression and transmission of panoramic video content. Our method enables personalized viewing by dynamically adjusting the video quality based on the user's view port, which leads to a reduction of the required data rate without reducing the perceived video quality. Specifically, we try to combine three core aspects which are the optimization of compression techniques which are tailored for panoramic content with individual user region awareness. Then the delivery framework that supports adaptive streaming based on real-time view port tracking to optimize the bandwidth usage, and finally a robust decompression pipeline that ensures a seamless video experience with minimal latency and no recognizable video quality loss. With this approach, our goal is to improve the scalability and user experience, especially for the VR panoramic video use case, which should allow access to panoramic video streams with reduced bandwidth requirements.

In the following work, the current State-of-the-Art (SotA) and recent advances in this research field will be reviewed in Chapter 2, as well as the necessary technical background and technologies. The motivation for improving this area, as well as the requirements to achieve our goals, will be provided in Chapter 3. In Chapter 4 our approach to optimizing video transmission will be presented, followed by an evaluation of different settings and the different benefits, as well as a comparison with current SotA and recent research in Chapter 5. Finally, Chapter 6 concludes this thesis and summarizes the results obtained and gives an overview of what can be done to further improve this work in the future.

Related Work & Background

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For the delivery of 360° videos, there are solutions in which all 360° content is streamed to users, regardless of the viewport position, which leads to an extreme waste of network resources. To address this problem, viewport prediction, tile-based streaming, and bitrate adaption are important procedures for adaptive 360° video streaming according to Yaqoob *et al.* [7]. Furthermore, Zhiyu Pang [8] stated that these three topics are currently the main research topics on 360° adaptive streaming. Therefore, this Section will dive into those areas and state the latest relevant findings for this thesis.

2.1 Viewport Prediction

The correct prediction of the user viewport is the main priority when it comes to efficient streaming of 360° video content. There exist two main prediction methods which can be classified as motion-based prediction stated by Xie *et al.* [9] and content-based prediction shown by Fan *et al.* [10].

Motion-based viewport prediction attempts to extrapolate the future viewport of users with the help of the sensors included in the Head-Mounted Display (HMD) by using historical motion information. According to Qian *et al.* [11], one problem that occurs here

Figure 2.1: User's visual fixation heat map on video frames described in Ban *et al.* [1].

is that the long-term viewport prediction is highly inaccurate and the accuracy decreases along with the prediction period.

The content-based method considers the visual saliency of the video to predict the viewport, but this leads to a high computational complexity due to the bias of users Region Of Interest (ROI). Ban *et al.* [1] came up with an approach in which most people are interested in one object within the picture, and when this is found, there is a good reason why other viewers also tend to have the same ROI. They verified this by analyzing a real head-movement trace dataset which is shown in Figure 2.1 as a heatmap. They combined the benefits of motion-based and content-based prediction by using Linear Regression (LR) for finding a motion-based fixation which then is combined with the content-based approach using the K-Nearest-Neighbors (KNN) algorithm. With that approach, they achieved an improvement of around 30% in bandwidth occupation and viewport quality variance compared to traditional viewport predictions.

2.1.1 Foveated Rendering

Another approach to improve video quality and reduce data that need to be handled by an HMD is foveated rendering. According to Wang *et al.* [12], it takes advantage of the inherent features of human eyes and renders different regions with different qualities without sacrificing perceived visual quality.

This concept is based on three main steps. The first step is to apply perceptual models of the human visual system to foveated rendering. The image is then rendered with varying levels of quality based on the foveation principles, and the foveated rendering is integrated into existing rendering paradigms to improve overall performance.

This is possible because the fovea region, the region where the visual system perceives the finest details, is just a small region of our whole visual field. As shown by Jabbireddy *et al.* [2], when using a VR-HMD, we only see that 4% of the screen pixels lie in the foveal region and the rest lie in the peripheral region. The importance in foveated rendering or also in viewport-related rendering can be seen in Figure 2.2, which shows what percentage of pixels are occupied by the fovea region.

Figure 2.2: Percentage of pixel in the foeva region described in Jabbireddy *et al.* [2].

2.2 Tile-based Streaming

Tile based streaming tries to utilize the known viewport of the user. To do so, the video needs to be separated into multiple parts, in this case into a variable number of tiles, where the client will then receive only the tiles in high quality that are within the ROI and the rest in lower quality, or they can even be neglected. Using the High Efficiency Video Coding (H.265/HEVC) described by Sullivan *et al.* [13] provides the benefit, when used with tiled videos, that standard video decoders can be used.

For streaming video content, the standardization of MPEG Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (DASH) described by Iraj Sodagar [14] can be used for 360° video adaption and performs similarly to traditional video content. The 360° video is spatially partitioned into a variable number of non-overlapping rectangular regions, which are the so-called tiles that all hold a Spatial Relation Description (SRD).

The SRD provides the spatial location of each video on a global grid, as described by Niamut *et al.* [15]. This tiled video is then further split into temporal fixed-duration segments. To be able to take advantage of those tiled segments, each tile is encoded in multiple bitrates, so that also multiple clients with different tile requirements can watch the same stream without a needed change on the server side.

On the client side, the viewport prediction algorithm decides which tiles to fetch and in what quality. In Figure 2.3, the whole process from getting an input image, encoding and DASH creation, and communication between the client and the server is shown in a simplified way.

2.3 Bitrate Adaption

For the client to be able to decide which tiles will be requested from the server, a bitrate adaption logic needs to be used because there is always a upper limit of bandwidth which

Figure 2.3: Overview of MPEG-DASH streaming with tiling proposed by Concolato *et al.* [3].

should not be exceeded.

In the DASH client implementation of the GPAC Open Source project by Le Feuvre *et al.* [16] the bitrate adaption logic is divided into three main steps. The first step is tile priority setup, where the DASH client first identifies the coding dependencies of each tile set when loading a Media Presentation Description (MPD) with SRD information. Then the media renderer is informed about the SRD details for each tile to adjust the layout based on the display size. Once the tile sets are identified, the priorities are assigned to the tiles, which is done every time when rate adaption needs to be performed.

The second step is the rate allocation, which gathers all the information on the throughput of the network and the bitrates of the tiles. With this information, the available bandwidth is distributed between the different tiles and their priority levels. The big difference to non-tiled scenarios is that the client needs to download multiple video segments at once and therefore decide with which bitrate the tiles are requested.

Once the bitrate for each tile is selected, the third step, the rate adaption is performed for each tile with a target bandwidth equal to the selected bitrate.

2.4 Content Delivery Networks

Content Delivery Networks (CDNs) have evolved significantly since the beginning of 2000 to provide a fast, reliable, and scalable distribution of digital content. A typical CDN consists of a network of geographically distributed cache servers which are designed to

Figure 2.4: Workflow of CDN proposed by Yang *et al.* [4].

reduce latency by delivering content to the user from the closest available server. When the user requests content, the request is routed through Domain Name System (DNS) and load balancers to select the optimal caching server. When the content is not already cached there, it is fetched from the origin server to deliver it, as explained by Yang *et al.* [4]. This core concept can be seen in Figure 2.4.

As there are multiple different use cases for media content delivery, there are also different types of CDNs, which was shown by Ali *et al.* [17]. To name some common ones, there are traditional CDNs which rely on dedicated edge servers, global replication, and DNS routing for latency control, such as Akamai Technologies [18], Cloudflare [19] or Amazon CloudFront [20].

Another well known CDN type is the cloud-based CDN which offers more flexible and scalable distribution tightly integrated with cloud services and elastic deployment as, for example, AWS [21] or Azure [22], and lastly there are local CDNs which are mainly used for network-specific optimizations or prototyping with the lack of global reach, such as Nginx [23] or Apache [24]. Of course, this is not the full list of CDNs available out there as Pathan *et al.* [25] already showed in 2007.

2.5 Video Compression Background

Citing Iain Richardson [26], "Compression is the act or process of compacting data into a smaller number of bits. Video compression (video coding) is the process of converting digital video into a format suitable for transmission or storage, whilst typically reducing the number of bits."

This act is also called encoding of digital videos, which is done by an encoder, and the decompression is called decoding which is processed by a decoder. This pair of encoder and decoder is called a codec. With those it is possible to compress for example a raw video of Full HD quality, which would take around 1.22 TB of storage into a few gigabytes without a noticeable reduction in quality. This compression can be lossless or lossy.

When lossy compression is used, the reconstructed stream is an approximation of the original and decreases the amount of redundant data without affecting subjective quality, while in lossless compression the reconstructed video stream is identical to the original, according to Eetu Latja [5]. Where lossless compression can achieve a compression ratio of about 3-4, lossy compression can achieve ratios from hundreds to thousands.

Another important part to mention is that the features that are used in image compression, shown by Marcellin *et al.* [27], containing predictions, transforms, quantization, and block coding, are also used in video compression.

2.5.1 Codec Structure

The codec structure consists of three main parts, a prediction model, a spatial model, and an entropy model. When encoding a video, the prediction model gets a raw video sequence where it tries to reduce redundancy by analyzing the correlation of adjacent video frames, producing residual frames that represent the differences between the original and the predicted frames. This technique is extensively discussed by Sullivan *et al.* [13].

The residual frames are then processed by the spatial model, which transforms the essential information into a few key components by changing it into a domain where most of the information is concentrated on a small number of samples. In this way, insignificant samples can be neglected which can be achieved using the Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT). This step is crucial to achieve high compression rates and is explained by Rao and Yip [28]. Afterwards, the remaining data are quantized, which means that the precision is adjusted to prepare it for efficient coding, as explained by A. Gersho [29].

The entropy encoder then takes these data along with the prediction parameters and applies statistical compression techniques to reduce redundancy. When those steps are completed, the final compressed bitstream is produced, which is ready to be stored or transmitted. This is the basic way of digital video processing as described by Tekalp [30].

This bitstream can then be decoded and reconstructed to a video by the decoder. The process there works in reverse, starting with the entropy decoder, which retrieves the transformed samples and prediction parameters. The residual frames are then reconstructed by the spatial model which are used together with the prediction parameters to produce the prediction frames by the prediction model. Finally, the original video, or an approximation of it if lossy compression was used, can be reconstructed by adding the residual and predicted frames.

2.5.2 Coding Standards

Based on this codec structure, coding standards were created, starting with the first ever digital video coding standard, H.120, which was introduced by the Comité Consultatif Internationale Télégraphique et Téléphonique (CCITT) (now known as International Telecommunication Union (Telecommunication Standardization Sector) (ITU-T)) [31] in 1984 for low-bitrate conferences over digital telephone networks. It used Differential Pulse Code Modulation (DPCM) with scalar quantization but had problems with limited visual quality and compression efficiency, so it was quickly replaced.

The first widely adapted standard was then H.261, introduced in 1990 also by the CCITT [32], which was created for video conferences over Integrated Services Digital Network (ISDN) networks. It used macroblocks and motion compensation to reduce redundancy between frames, which is the basis for modern video coding techniques.

Shortly after, in 1993, MPEG-1 was developed to enable video and audio storage on digital media, especially for CDs. This also introduced the MP3 audio format, which were both created by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO/IEC) [33]. To support higher quality videos for television broadcasting and DVDs, MPEG-2 was introduced in 1995, also by ISO/IEC [34], which allowed higher bitrates, scalable quality, and interlaced video, which created the standard for satellite TV. Around the same time, H.263 was created by ITU-T [35] for low-bitrate applications such as Internet streaming and mobile video application, offering better motion compensation than H.261.

With the introduction of MPEG-4 by ISO/IEC [36] in 1998, more versatility with features such as object-based coding, sprites and improved error resilience was possible. This improvement made early interactive mobile multimedia applications possible. The next big improvement in video compression was then made again by ITU-T with the introduction of Advanced Video Coding (H.264/AVC) in 2003 [37]. With innovations like variable block sizes for motion compensation, Context-Adaptive Binary Arithmetic Coding (CABAC), and improved prediction models, H.264/AVC became the standard for high-definition video, used for online streaming, video conferences, and Blu-ray discs.

As video resolution increased to 4K and 8k, the previously mentioned H.265/HEVC codec was introduced in 2013 as the successor to H.264/AVC by ISO/IEC [38]. It provides even better compression efficiency by introducing larger coding units, better motion prediction, independent tile processing, and support for High Dynamic Range (HDR) videos and achieves approximately a 50% better bitrate reduction compared to its predecessor while maintaining the same visual quality. This codec is widely used for 4K UHD Blu-rays, video streaming services, and broadcasting. In addition, multiple extensions were created for different scenarios which will be explained in Section 2.5.3.

The most current development is Versatile Video Coding (H.266/VVC), which was introduced in 2020 as an improvement of H.265/HEVC to support ultra-high-resolution video, such as 8K, as well as immersive applications like virtual and augmented reality. According to Bross *et al.* [39], it achieves even better compression efficiency with adaptive

Figure 2.5: Frame division in H.265/HEVC with CTUs in gray and tiles in black shown by Eetu Latja *et al.* [5] on the right and overlaid to a real picture on the left.

block sizes and improved handling of complex video scenes.

Due to licensing fees of H.265/HEVC, a royalty free, open-source codec, the AV1 [40], was introduced in 2018 by the Alliance for Open Media. It was optimized for web streaming and is now used by streaming platforms like YouTube, Netflix, or Twitch. In addition, Google developed video codecs as open-source alternatives, the VP8 [41], which should compete with H.264/AVC in real-time streaming and later in 2013, the VP9 [42] to be able to reach the same compression efficiency without additional licensing fees. This codec is widely adopted by services created by Google.

2.5.3 H.265 Extensions

One of the main features of H.265/HEVC is the possibility of improving parallelism with the introduction of tiles. The tiles divide the picture into rows and columns where each tile contains multiple Coding Tree Units (CTUs). The division of a frame with 18×12 CTUs into 9 tiles of equal size is shown in Figure 2.5. With those tile boundaries, a break in coding dependencies is created, specifically entropy coding and reconstruction dependencies are not allowed across tile boundaries. This includes motion vector prediction, intra prediction, and context selection.

The only exception which is allowed across the boundaries is in-loop filtering, but this can be disabled by a flag in the bit-stream. As shown by Misra *et al.* [43] with this version, parallel processing of tiles is possible, and only the locations of the tiles must be signaled in the bit stream with an offset of all but the first tile.

With Wavefront Parallel Processing (WPP), the CTUs of a frame are encoded in such a way that the encoding of a CTU never brakes the interdependencies by processing them in a natural order. The CTUs always depend on their left, top-left, top, and top right neighbor, as shown by Radicke *et al.* [44]. The main advantage is that it scales naturally with the video resolution and the number of available processing units.

One standardized extension of H.265/HEVC is scalable High Efficiency Video Coding,

which uses a multi-loop scalable coding architecture. As described in further detail by Boyce *et al.* [45], it supports conventional scalability features such as temporal, spatial, and Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) scalability with new features such as hybrid codec, bit depth scalability, and Coarse Granular Scalable (CGS).

Two other extensions were developed by JCT-3V for H.265/HEVC, the multi-view High Efficiency Video Coding and 3D-HEVC. MV-HEVC comprises only high level syntax additions and can be implemented using existing single-layer decoding cores, where higher compression is achieved by exploiting redundancy between different camera views of the same scene. The 3D-HEVC introduces new compression tools that explicitly address the unique characteristics of depth maps and exploit dependencies between multiple views as well as between video texture and depth, which leads to a more efficient compression. As stated by Tech *et al.* [46], 3D-HEVC provides benefits primarily in scenarios which require video texture and depth, for example in more advanced 3D displays, due to the video-plus-depth compression format.

2.6 Color Space Background

Citing Ford and Roberts [47] "A colour space is a method by which we can specify, create and visualise colour. As humans, we may define a colour by its attributes of brightness, hue and colourfulness. A computer may describe a colour using the amounts of red, green and blue phosphor emission required to match a colour. A printing press may produce a specific colour in terms of the reflectance and absorbance of cyan, magenta, yellow and black inks on the printing paper."

Although the RGB/A color space is definitely the most known and used, as can be seen in Figure 2.6 presenting the popularity of color spaces for OpenCV by Podpora *et al.* [6], this gives a good introduction to why there is not only one color space available, as the decision which one to use depends on the kind of application.

2.6.1 RGB and RGBA

The RGB (Red Green Blue) color space is an additive color system, where the color space can be obtained by drawing a triangle on a special color chart, where each base color serves as an endpoint. This model is often extended by an alpha channel when used in computer graphics, giving the RGBA color space. This added channel represents the opacity or transparency as shown in the work of Porter and Duff [48] in 1984, where they present a formal mathematical framework for the influence of the alpha channel, which is still a fundamental for computer graphics.

2.6.2 YUV and YCbCr

Another widely used color space is the YUV color space, which separates RGB into luminance, which is a weighted sum of gamma-corrected RGB values stored in Y, and

Figure 2.6: Popularity of the most popular color representations based on the Google hit count for 41 most popular OpenCV format conversion functions proposed by Podpora *et al.* [6]

chrominance information stored in U and V. Historically seen, the term YUV was used for analog encoding, as it comes from the beginning of analog television systems, where U and V were added with the introduction of color TVs as described by Étienne Dupuis [49]. As part of the development of a worldwide video standard, the YUV color space was redefined as YCbCr, where Cb holds the chrominance difference for blue and Cr the red difference. Equations were laid out to fit these three components, mostly still known as Y, U, and V, in the range of 0-255.

Stated by Gordon *et al.* [50], the YUV format concentrates most of the image information on the luminance value. Therefore, most compression algorithms compress only every other U and V element in the horizontal direction, where the missing elements are reconstructed by either interpolation or duplication.

2.6.3 Color Space Conversion

As most digital displays use the RGB/A color space to present the image, a transformation for the different color spaces must be performed. The YUV color model is used in image and video compression applications, shown in the work of Koju and Joshi [51], such as MPEG-1, MPEG-2, MPEG-4, H.261, H.262, H.263, H.264, H.265, JPEG and many more.

The conversion from YUV to RGBA can be performed with the formulas shown in 2.1 to 2.3, which is a component-wise form of the matrix version shown by Étienne Dupuis [49], showing the International Telecommunication Union((Radiocommunication Sector)) (ITU-R) BT.601 standardized values. When the RGB values are obtained, the alpha channel is typically set to fully opaque, unless transparency data is available from other sources.

$$R = 1.164 \times (Y - 16) + 1.596 \times (V - 128), \quad (2.1)$$

$$G = 1.164 \times (Y - 16) - 0.392 \times (U - 128) - 0.813 \times (V - 128), \quad (2.2)$$

$$B = 1.164 \times (Y - 16) + 2.017 \times (U - 128). \quad (2.3)$$

In practical implementations, these floating point multiplications are computationally expensive, therefore the equations are often reformulated to be able to work with integer arithmetic. This can be done by scaling and bit shifting, revealing the following formulas shown in 2.4 to 2.6, which gives an approximation of the RGB channels but drastically increases the efficiency. Worth mentioning is that, depending on the standard used by the compression, different coefficients need to be used for the conversion, and, of course, also for the fixed-point integer version.

$$R \approx \frac{298 \times (Y - 16) + 409 \times (V - 128) + 128}{256}, \quad (2.4)$$

$$G \approx \frac{298 \times (Y - 16) - 100 \times (U - 128) - 208 \times (V - 128) + 128}{256}, \quad (2.5)$$

$$B \approx \frac{298 \times (Y - 16) + 516 \times (U - 128) + 128}{256}. \quad (2.6)$$

2.7 Streaming Protocols Background

As the way data is transmitted over the Internet is an always improving topic, there are also multiple different protocols which were implemented and adopted, where each of them has individual improvements regarding stability, latency or a broad range of use cases. This includes video on demand, live streaming, conferencing, etc. which all have different requirements.

The following Section provides an overview of the most commonly used protocols nowadays, including Real Time Messaging Protocol (RTMP), Real Time Streaming Protocol (RTSP), HTTP Live Streaming (HLS) and Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (DASH) and shows their individual benefits. In addition, recent advances in low-latency streaming will be presented.

2.7.1 Real Time Streaming Protocol

Schulzrinne *et al.* [52] present with Real Time Streaming Protocol (RTSP) an application-level protocol for control over the delivery of data with real-time properties. RTSP provides an extensible framework to enable the controlled on-demand delivery of real-time data, such as audio and video.

Meanwhile, there is a second version of RTSP which obsoletes the version 1.0 defined in RFC2326 from Schulzrinne, Rao and Lanphier [53]. This protocol can be used with

delivery channels such as User Datagram Protocol (UDP), multicast UDP, and Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) and is capable of controlling multiple sessions at once. The syntax and structure of the protocol are similar to the HTTP protocol, but add new request methods such as PLAY, PAUSE, SETUP, DESCRIBE, and TEARDOWN. The URL of RTSP is also very similar, with the only difference in the scheme used `rtsp://` in RTSP instead of `http://` in the HTTP protocol, as described by Santos-González *et al.* [54].

2.7.2 Real Time Messaging Protocol

The Real Time Messaging Protocol (RTMP) developed by Adobe [55] was designed to provide high-performance transmission of audio, video, and data between the Adobe Flash platform technologies. RTMP is available as an open specification to create products and technologies that enable the delivery of video, audio and data in open AMF, SWF, FLV, and F4V formats which are compatible with Adobe Flash Player.

In comparison to the RTSP, which usually works over UDP, RTMP operate on top of TCP, which maintains persistent connection and makes it reliable to transmit all video content.

Although Flash technology is now obsolete, RTMP has still a key role as a streaming protocol used, for example, by YouTube Live [56], Twitch [57], or Facebook Live [58]. It is also often used for broadcasting to streaming servers, where it is transcoded into HTTP-based formats for distribution to end users.

2.7.3 HTTP-Livestreaming

The HTTP Live Streaming (HLS) protocol developed by Apple Inc. [59] is an HTTP-based adaptive bitrate protocol which is widely used in media players, web browsers, mobile devices, and streaming media servers. HLS splits the overall stream into a sequence of small HTTP-based file downloads, where the stream can be encoded at different bitrates. These files can then be requested by the client using an extended M3U playlist file, which allows the client to decide on the bitrate that the current stream sequence should be loaded according to the current network condition, without causing delays.

Due to the use of HTTP as the base, it benefits from existing CDNs and is compatible with most firewalls and NAT setups. Commonly used segment times of 6-10 seconds result in high end-to-end latency, making it less suitable for interactive applications.

2.7.4 Dynamic Adaptive Streaming Over HTTP

Not different from the HLS protocol, the DASH protocol developed by MPEG [60] also provides segmented video content at multiple bitrate levels, allowing for adaption to the network condition. This information is provided to the client with a DASH Media Presentation Description (MPD). It is a pull-based bitrate streaming standard in which the

client device plays the central role by deciding on the video adaptation. The client can select the HTTP-based file with the highest bitrate possible that can be downloaded in time for playback without causing delays or rebuffering events.

Compared to HLS, DASH is codec-agnostic and is standardized as an open international protocol. By providing fine-grained control over segment size and encoding ladders, it is highly suitable for large-scale VOD deployments, which can be seen by the adoption on platforms such as Netflix [61] or Amazon Prime Video [62].

2.7.5 Low Latency Streaming

For both streaming versions, HLS and DASH, low latency adaptations were created with slightly different approaches. The Low Latency DASH (LL-DASH) [63] extension was first introduced in 2018 and was added to the standard in 2019, followed by Low Latency HLS (LL-HLS) [64] introduced in 2019.

The main difference between the traditional streaming methods and the low latency ones is the reduction of segment durations, optimizing the segmentation mechanism and the HTTP protocol. Where LL-DASH uses chunked transfer encoding (CTE) to progressively send segments as smaller chunks, LL-HLS uses partial segments, which are smaller video fragments within a full segment that can be requested separately.

According to Bentaleb *et al.* [65], who compared these two different approaches, LL-DASH can achieve latencies as low as 1.5-3 seconds with the use of HTTP/1.1 while LL-HLS was able to achieve nearly similar results by the use of HTTP/2. The main problem that came up with the low latency extensions is that the existing adaptive bitrate decisions cannot be used directly, and new solutions for that need to be found.

Motivation & Requirements

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The distribution of videos to multiple devices at once, where each user is focusing on a different part of the stream, is gaining importance with the increase of high quality VR devices such as the Apple Vision Pro¹ or the Meta Quest 3² and also on mobile and flat screen devices with Pan-Tilt-Zoom (PTZ) operations to move the virtual camera. This has been developed in both research and industry, which can be seen in the number of papers represented by Jeppsson *et al.* [66]. Finding the sweet spot between latency, video quality, and bandwidth usage is crucial and very different compared to standard 2D video streaming. One of the main advantages of the H.265/HEVC codec is that the tiling is already in their standard, and when this is combined with DASH-SRD the basis is already there to provide different view qualities to multiple devices. Shown in the work of Sánchez De La Fuente *et al.* [67], with the use of the H.265 extension scalable High Efficiency Video Coding (SHVC) and multi-view High Efficiency Video Coding (MV-HEVC) the peak streaming bitrate can be reduced while the ROI changes. This is vital for a high immersion experience because stutter or poor quality while moving within a VR device can not only worsen the experience but also lead to cybersickness, which causes symptoms such as nausea, fatigue, headache, stress or vomiting, as described by Martirosov *et al.* [68]. This led to the idea to create a server application that is capable of tiling H.265/HEVC 360° live-videos received over RTMP and provide it to the clients via DASH with high fidelity. The client application should run on Android devices, including mobile phones and VR headsets, which can receive this stream via the DASH protocol, with only the tiles

¹<https://www.apple.com/apple-vision-pro/>

²<https://www.meta.com/quest/quest-3/>

downloaded in high quality that are actually in view, then recreate a fully not tiled video and provide it to the users with nearly real time properties and without any noticeable quality loss due to the lower quality tiles which are not directly seen.

3.1 Requirements

Basically the requirements for this project can be separated into two main parts, server-based and client-based. In this Section a short overview of those main requirements will be shown and later in Section 4, the realization of them will be presented.

3.2 Server-Side Requirements

In general the server needs to be able to let an external device stream a live 360° video to it, then process the received video, so it is represented in tiles, each with multiple quality levels, and provide it in an efficient way to the clients, so that they can decide on their own what tile is downloaded in what quality.

3.2.1 RTMP Listener

To start with the project, a Linux based server which is capable of creating a stable RTMP listener, which is accessible over the network, so that a camera can send the video data to it, needs to be created. The need for RTMP comes from the fact that it maintains a persistent connection based on top of TCP, which makes it more reliable as described in Section 2.7.

3.2.2 Tiling The Video

When the server is capable of receiving the video stream, it now has to process the video into multiple individual tiles and qualities. To be able to do this, a H.265/HEVC encoded video coming from the RTMP listener is required, as the H.265/HEVC standard already makes use of the tiling concept. Further constraints are that the tiling can only be done with a width and height of multiple of 64 and the input format has to be of yuv420p. In addition, the desired number of quality levels and the quality level itself need to be decided in this step.

3.2.3 DASH Creation

After having the video stream in multiple quality tiles, they need to be stored on the server in a way that makes them distinguishable so that a client can later easily find the correct tile with regard to the correct time, location and quality level. To make them storable, segments of the full tiled streams need to be saved, as the client needs to be able

to download them separately. This segment time needs to be declared in this step and with that information the MPD file can be created which allows the client to find all files.

3.2.4 Content Delivery

Lastly on the server side, the created files need to be made available over the network so they can really be accessed. For that a file-based web-server needs to be set up which can make the video segments available without much delay. For that, it is important that the read and write operations on the hard drive be reduced to a minimum as they are very costly. Also, the server needs to let the same client download multiple files for the time the live stream lasts, as all tiles of one video segment need to be loaded at every segment interval.

3.3 Client-Side Requirements

The client needs to be able to represent the tiled live video to the user with the lowest possible download rate, while still providing the best user experience. To achieve that, an efficient way needs to be found to calculate the correct tile quality and make them visible on the client's screen in a real-time manner.

3.3.1 DASH Download

To start on the client side, the information on how the stream is set up is needed from the server. To get this information, the MPD file is downloaded from the server and the information about video size, tile setup, the segment lengths and video times needs to be extracted. In addition, a linkage between the tile position, tile quality, and the index of the associated files that need to be downloaded needs to be made.

3.3.2 Tile Quality Selection

After extraction of the information embedded in the MPD file, the tile configuration can be defined on the client sphere, which is necessary to find out which tiles to download in what quality. Therefore, the field of view of the client needs to be known, as well as the current view direction. With this information, the tile quality of each individual tile can be selected and connected to the file that needs to be downloaded.

3.3.3 Rearranging Downloaded Tiles

When the tiles are selected, they need to be downloaded as fast as possible, optimally in parallel. Then, all tiles need to be concatenated with a so-called initialization file in the correct order, which is line-by-line from top to bottom. This concatenated file is then used to recreate a playable video file, which shows all the tiles in the correct order and quality and has a length of the server-defined segment length.

3.3.4 Displaying The Video

After a playable video is created, now the video must be displayed on the client's device. Therefore, it is necessary that the device is capable of decoding the H.265/HEVC encoded video and show it on the screen without any noticeable delay. As we are talking here mainly about spherical videos for the 360° case, the mapping of the pixel onto the video sphere also needs to be done correctly, so no unwanted tilts or distortions occur on the device.

3.3.5 Seamless Video Playback

To achieve a seamless transition between the individual segments of the video, the next video segment must be downloaded, concatenated, and prepared to be displayed on the device before the current segment finished playing. The timing of those procedures needs to be set in such a way that there is no big latency between the currently last available video segment of the video, so we are as close as possible to real-time streaming. At the same time, it must be ensured that the segments are not downloaded too early as the clients view direction can always change and the tile qualities are selected according to it.

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To improve the State-of-the-Art H.265/HEVC live streaming, we decided to build a server application which is capable of receiving a live RTMP stream which is then transcoded to a tiled DASH stream of multiple bitrate that can be accessed through a Web server. For the client side, we decided to create a Unity application, which is responsible for the bitrate and tile adaption of the DASH stream, to represent the 360° video in the most efficient way.

4.1 Conceptual Design

We started by creating a Linux-based server, which runs the GPAC multimedia framework to be able to run an RTMP server, which is capable of receiving a H.265/HEVC stream from a network camera to fulfill our first server requirement stated in Section 3.2.

When the stream is received, we make use of FFmpeg and the Kvazaar encoder to be able to tile the stream into multiple qualities and tile sizes, with what we were able to satisfy the second server requirement. The GPAC framework is then used to generate the DASH files for our tiled stream. This includes the MPD file, which provides the metadata for the stream, the initialization files, which are required for video and audio recreation, the tiled video segments, and the audio files.

With that done, only the last requirement on the server side is missing, which is the delivery of the created data to the clients, which we have realized with an Nginx server that is capable of distributing the data on the Web.

Figure 4.1: Representation of the workflow for live 360° tiled DASH video streaming. The separation of the client and server implementation is highlighted to see what implementation part belongs only to the client or only to the server.

Now to start with the client side, we decided to work on an Unity project for Android devices, which can be run on mobile phone devices as well as on HMD-VR devices. To download the correct files from the server, we implemented a MPD parser in C#, which extracts all the information needed to get the correct segment numbers, as well as the correct tile indices for quality control, fulfilling our first requirement as described in Section 3.3.

For loading the correct tile, we now need the viewport of the client as well as the tiles which are currently fully visible, partially visible, and non-visible. To get that information, we project a grid with the same tiling as in the MPD file onto a sphere and check via the camera transform and rotation parameters which tiles need to be downloaded in what quality levels.

Now, as the second requirement is met, we download the correct tiles and need to rearrange them in a way that we get a playable video, which is done by concatenating the initialization file with the tiles in left to right and top to bottom order. This is then fed into a cross-compiled C++ GPAC library with Kvazaar included, which creates a playable video file out of it.

By fulfilling the third requirement, we now have to display the created video to the user, which is done by mapping the video into the inside of a sphere, while placing the camera in the middle of it. With a simple shader, the distortions of the spherical video are corrected so that the user can see the video in good quality. This entire pipeline is visualized in Figure 4.1, where all individual parts can be easily identified.

As all the individual parts are now done, to finish the application, we needed to find a way to have a seamless video playback, which we did by downloading and preparing the following segment while the current video is displayed to the user. The preparation includes all the previously described tasks, including position estimation for tile selection, downloading and concatenating the correct tiles, combining them to a playable video, and mapping them onto the sphere. Then we wait until the current video is finished and start the whole process again.

With that done, all the requirements of our projects described in Chapter 3 are met, and the application is ready to be used. In the following Sections, a detailed version of the implementation will be presented.

4.2 Server-Side Implementation

To be able to receive a live 360° video and process it in a way that it can be accessed at multiple bit rates by a client device, we created a server infrastructure based on the Ubuntu 22.04 [69] operating system. The main applications which were needed to achieve this were the GPAC multimedia framework, already briefly introduced in Section 2.3, the Kvazaar encoder developed by Ultravideo [70] and Nginx created by Igor Sysoev [23] which servers as the Web server to distribute the processed data.

4.2.1 Server Setup

To start with the setup of the mentioned libraries, the main underlying library FFmpeg introduced by Fabrice Bellard [71] needed to be modified. It is the leading multimedia framework which is capable of decoding, encoding, transcoding, muxing, demuxing, streaming, filtering, and playing pretty much anything video-related. It also serves as the backbone of the used GPAC framework used in this work. For FFmpeg to be able to tile the H.265/HEVC incoming video stream, the Kvazaar library was needed to be compiled into the FFmpeg build together with the x265 extension, which is not enabled by default due to licensing problems which are already stated in Section 2.5.2.

With those libraries compiled and ready, the GPAC framework was configured to start an RTMP server via the underlying FFmpeg library. This server waits for a live video, which can then be further processed. When a video is received by the RTMP server, it is piped to the encoders, for the creation of the video tiles to the Kvazaar encoder and for the audio encoding to the Advanced Audio Coding (aac) encoder created by MPEG [72], which is also provided by the FFmpeg library. The output of the encoders is then processed by GPACs DASH filter, which can take several inputs. In our case, multiple tiled H.265/HEVC encoded video streams at different bit rates and one aac audio stream. These are then packed as a live DASH stream containing the MPD file and all needed segment files which are then stored in a dedicated storage space mounted as Temporary File System (tmpfs).

To efficiently serve the generated data to the clients, we decided to set up the Nginx Web server as a file server linked to the dedicated tmpfs storage space, which enables seamless data publication of constantly generated DASH files. The primary motivation to use the tmpfs file system is the ability to bypass the costly read and write operations on a traditional hard drive, as all data is kept in virtual memory. Furthermore, since our focus is the creation of efficient live video transportation, the temporary nature of the tmpfs aligns perfectly with our needs. The only crucial thing that we need to keep track of by using the tmpfs is that we have to allocate enough of our RAM storage for the tiled DASH stream created, to prevent memory shortages during operation.

4.2.2 Tiling The 360° Video

To tile the incoming video, it has to satisfy two requirements, namely that the width and height have to be a multiple of 64, because otherwise when merging the bitstream, it will lead to decoding artifacts. The other requirement is that the input video format needs to be yuv420p for 8-bit videos or yuv420p-10le for 10-bit videos, because the Kvazaar encoder is only able to handle those two formats.

Then to be able to later on DASH the video, the encoder needs to be configured that the tiles are constrained in motion prediction and each tile is encapsulated in one slice. Putting multiple tiles in a slice will not work, since the slices Network Abstraction Layer Unit (NALU) will not be split in different tracks, which prevents the download of individual tiles in DASH. This can be simply done by telling the encoder that each tile needs to be encapsulated by a separate tile, and the motion vectors are also restricted to the frame of the tile.

With those restrictions, we are able to create a 360° video which is separated into individual tiles which are also individually downloadable and can be interchanged. But when we want to change one tile, we have to make sure that the encoded video has the same Sequence Parameter Set (SPS)/Picture Parameter Set (PPS)/Video Parameter Set (VPS) and Quantization Parameter (QP) setting. Due to this constraint, the settings can only be specified globally for all different desired tile qualities, with only the bitrate that is used for the encoding of the different quality tiles being configurable.

The only part left that needs to be configured, required for tiling the video into multiple qualities, which in our case means different bitrates, is to define a rate control algorithm and specify that the encoder forces an interframe in a specified period. This is necessary because the Group of Pictures (GOP)s need to be enforced properly in time, as the Kvazaar encoder cannot close a GOP at any other place than its specified period. This is also necessary because it cannot be ensured that the source will not drop a frame because the server is receiving live videos. Also, if you want to interchange tiles with tiles from another video source, the different source videos need to have the same resolution, bit depth, and tiling grid.

Now it is possible to receive a live 360° video over RTMP, set up the global settings

```
1  #gpac input parameter to start an
2  #rtmp server listening on port 1935
3  gpac -i rtmp://localhost:1935/live/stream:gpac:rtmp_listen:FID=S \
4
5  #kvazaar parameters passed as global meta arguments
6  --kvazaar-params=input-res=3840x1920,input-fps=25,tiles=8x4,\
7  slices=tiles,mv-constraint=frametile,rc-algorithm=lambda \
8
9  #first encoding at 20 mbps with tile splitter,
10 #forcing intra every second
11 enc:SID=S:c=libkvazaar:b=20m:fintra=1:rc @ tilesplit:FID=V1 \
12
13 #second encoding at 1 mbps with tile splitter,
14 #forcing intra every second
15 enc:SID=S:c=libkvazaar:b=1m:fintra=1:rc @ tilesplit:FID=V2 \
16
17 #encoding audio with aac at 128kbps
18 enc:SID=S:c=aac:b=128k:FID=A1 \
```

Listing 4.1: GPAC parameters for receiving an RTMP stream and processing it into two tile qualities with an 8×4 tile layout.

of the video encoder, and specify the desired bitrate for the different qualities of the tile streams that are prepared for conversion into the DASH format to be downloadable by a client. Of course, the encoder can be configured in much more detail, which will be shown in Section 5.2, where the different settings will be compared. For now, the command on the server is as shown in the Listing 4.1.

This now includes the whole procedure of receiving the video over rtmp, setting up the configuration for the tiled encoders, as well as the audio encoder, where the outputs of the encoders are available separately and can then be processed by the DASH creator.

4.2.3 DASH Creation

To create a DASH format from the content produced by the encoders, the GPAC DASH creator needs to know which inputs it should take and with which DASH profile and mode the MPD file, the base file for the tracks and the individual track segments should be created. The MPD will contain as many adaption sets as there are tile tracks and base tracks in the source video and each tile adaption set will contain the representation for each specified quality. By setting the DASH mode to dynamic, the DASH profile to live and the `segdur` to two, it creates a live version of the MPD file, where each segment has a length of two seconds, which fits our encoder setting of forcing an intra frame every second, where it is important that the segment duration is a multiple of the intra frame creation. Without further specification, it holds the segments of the last 30 seconds to ensure that

```
1 -o live.mpd:gpac:SID=V1,V2,A1:dmode=dynamic:profile=live:segdur=2
```

Listing 4.2: GPAC output parameter for the creation of the live DASH format with two video and one audio source splitted into two second segments.

```
1 <?xml version="1.0"?>
2 <MPD xmlns="urn:mpeg:dash:schema:mpd:2011" minBufferTime="PT1.000S" type="dynamic" availabilityStartTime="2025-03-04T07:52:23.428Z" publishTime="2025-03-04T07:52:27.853Z"
3   minUpdatePeriod="PT0H0M1.000S" tnsShiftBufferDepth="PT0H0M30.000S" maxSegmentDuration="PT0H0M1.003S" profiles="urn:mpeg:dash:profile:live:2011">
4 <Period id="D101" start="PT0H0M0.000S">
5   <AdaptationSet segmentAlignment="true" mimeType="audio/mp4" startWithSAP="1">
6     <SegmentTemplate media="audio_dash_track2_SNumber$.m4s" initialization="audio_dash_track2_init.mp4" timescale="1000" presentationTimeOffset="599400" startNumber="1" duration="1000"/>
7     <Representation id="1" codecs="mp4a.40.2" audioSamplingRate="48000" bandwidth="128000">
8       <AudioChannelConfiguration schemeIdUri="urn:mpeg:dash:23003:3:audio_channel_configuration:2011" value="2"/>
9     </Representation>
10  </AdaptationSet>
11  <AdaptationSet segmentAlignment="true" maxWidth="3840" maxHeight="1920" maxFrameRate="25" par="2:1" bitstreamSwitching="true" mimeType="video/mp4" startWithSAP="1">
12    <EssentialProperty schemeIdUri="urn:mpeg:dash:srd:2014" value="1,0,0,0,3840,1920"/>
13    <SegmentTemplate media="video_dash_track1_SNumber$.m4s" initialization="video_dash_track1_init.mp4" timescale="1000" presentationTimeOffset="599400" startNumber="1" duration="1000"/>
14    <Representation id="4" codecs="hvt1.1.6.L186.80" width="3840" height="1920" frameRate="25" sar="1:1" bandwidth="100000">
15    </Representation>
16  </AdaptationSet>
17  <AdaptationSet segmentAlignment="true" maxWidth="1920" maxHeight="960" maxFrameRate="25" par="2:1" bitstreamSwitching="true" mimeType="video/mp4" startWithSAP="1">
18    <SupplementalProperty schemeIdUri="urn:mpeg:dash:srd:2014" value="1,0,0,1920,960"/>
19    <SegmentTemplate initialization="video_dash_track1_init.mp4"/>
20    <Representation id="4" codecs="hvt1.1.6.L186.80" width="1920" height="960" frameRate="25" sar="1:1" bandwidth="5007500" dependencyId="2">
21    <SegmentTemplate media="video_tile1_dash_track2_SNumber$.rep1.m4s" timescale="1000" presentationTimeOffset="599400" startNumber="1" duration="1000"/>
22    </Representation>
23    <Representation id="8" codecs="hvt1.1.6.L186.80" width="1920" height="960" frameRate="25" sar="1:1" bandwidth="257500" dependencyId="2">
24    <SegmentTemplate media="video_tile1_dash_track2_SNumber$.rep2.m4s" timescale="1000" presentationTimeOffset="599400" startNumber="1" duration="1000"/>
25    </Representation>
26  </AdaptationSet>
27  <AdaptationSet segmentAlignment="true" maxWidth="1920" maxHeight="960" maxFrameRate="25" par="2:1" bitstreamSwitching="true" mimeType="video/mp4" startWithSAP="1">
28    <SupplementalProperty schemeIdUri="urn:mpeg:dash:srd:2014" value="1,1920,0,1920,960"/>
29    <SegmentTemplate initialization="video_dash_track1_init.mp4"/>
30    <Representation id="5" codecs="hvt1.1.6.L186.80" width="1920" height="960" frameRate="25" sar="1:1" bandwidth="5007500" dependencyId="2">
31    <SegmentTemplate media="video_tile2_dash_track3_SNumber$.rep1.m4s" timescale="1000" presentationTimeOffset="599400" startNumber="1" duration="1000"/>
32    </Representation>
33    <Representation id="9" codecs="hvt1.1.6.L186.80" width="1920" height="960" frameRate="25" sar="1:1" bandwidth="257500" dependencyId="2">
34    <SegmentTemplate media="video_tile2_dash_track3_SNumber$.rep2.m4s" timescale="1000" presentationTimeOffset="599400" startNumber="1" duration="1000"/>
35    </Representation>
36  </AdaptationSet>
37  <AdaptationSet segmentAlignment="true" maxWidth="1920" maxHeight="960" maxFrameRate="25" par="2:1" bitstreamSwitching="true" mimeType="video/mp4" startWithSAP="1">
38    <SupplementalProperty schemeIdUri="urn:mpeg:dash:srd:2014" value="1,0,960,1920,960"/>
39    <SegmentTemplate initialization="video_dash_track1_init.mp4"/>
40    <Representation id="6" codecs="hvt1.1.6.L186.80" width="1920" height="960" frameRate="25" sar="1:1" bandwidth="5007500" dependencyId="2">
41    <SegmentTemplate media="video_tile3_dash_track4_SNumber$.rep1.m4s" timescale="1000" presentationTimeOffset="599400" startNumber="1" duration="1000"/>
42    </Representation>
43    <Representation id="10" codecs="hvt1.1.6.L186.80" width="1920" height="960" frameRate="25" sar="1:1" bandwidth="257500" dependencyId="2">
44    <SegmentTemplate media="video_tile3_dash_track4_SNumber$.rep2.m4s" timescale="1000" presentationTimeOffset="599400" startNumber="1" duration="1000"/>
45    </Representation>
46  </AdaptationSet>
47  <AdaptationSet segmentAlignment="true" maxWidth="1920" maxHeight="960" maxFrameRate="25" par="2:1" bitstreamSwitching="true" mimeType="video/mp4" startWithSAP="1">
48    <SupplementalProperty schemeIdUri="urn:mpeg:dash:srd:2014" value="1,1920,960,1920,960"/>
49    <SegmentTemplate initialization="video_dash_track1_init.mp4"/>
50    <Representation id="7" codecs="hvt1.1.6.L186.80" width="1920" height="960" frameRate="25" sar="1:1" bandwidth="5007500" dependencyId="2">
51    <SegmentTemplate media="video_tile4_dash_track5_SNumber$.rep1.m4s" timescale="1000" presentationTimeOffset="599400" startNumber="1" duration="1000"/>
52    </Representation>
53    <Representation id="11" codecs="hvt1.1.6.L186.80" width="1920" height="960" frameRate="25" sar="1:1" bandwidth="257500" dependencyId="2">
54    <SegmentTemplate media="video_tile4_dash_track5_SNumber$.rep2.m4s" timescale="1000" presentationTimeOffset="599400" startNumber="1" duration="1000"/>
55    </Representation>
56  </AdaptationSet>
57 </Period>
58 </MPD>
```

Figure 4.2: MPD file generated by the GPAC command for 2x2 tiling of a 3840x1920 video with two different bit rates.

no sudden jumps occur if rebuffering is needed and clears out all older segments, which helps to ensure that the `tmpfs` does not run out of storage space.

To complete the previously shown GPAC command, the last missing line for converting the received and processed stream into the DASH format is shown in the Listing 4.2. Here, the outputs of the encoders V1, V2, and A1 are taken to produce the DASH files. This command creates the MPD file, which contains information on how the individual tracks must be assembled. It also creates two initialization files, one for the audio track and one for the video track, along with two second segments of the audio and video tracks together with two second segments of each video tile at different bitrates. The MPD file now contains the information on where the media resources are located, the duration, size, and position of each fragment, and also the tile quality and the appropriate position and size. A small representation of a 2×2 tiled 3840×1920 video with a frame rate of 25 frames per second and one second segments can be seen in Figure 4.2.

In this MPD file, each track is now packed into one `AdaptationSet`. This holds for the

```
1 <AdaptationSet segmentAlignment="true" maxWidth="3840" maxHeight="1920"
2   maxFrameRate="25" par="2:1" bitstreamSwitching="true"
3   mimeType="video/mp4" startWithSAP="1">
4   <EssentialProperty schemeIdUri="urn:mpeg:dash:srd:2014"
5     value="1,0,0,0,0,3840,1920"/>
6   <SegmentTemplate media="video1_dash_track1_${Number$.m4s"
7     initialization="video1_dash_track1_init.mp4" timescale="1000"
8     presentationTimeOffset="599400" startNumber="1" duration="1000"/>
9   <Representation id="2" codecs="hvc2.1.6.L186.80" width="3840"
10    height="1920" frameRate="25" sar="1:1" bandwidth="10000">
11   </Representation>
12 </AdaptationSet>
```

Listing 4.3: MPD AdaptationSet of the overall video, necessary for reassembling the individual tiles to a playable format.

overall DASH track, which corresponds to the base tile track with `hvc2` codec, which ensures that the individual tracks correspond to tile tracks 1-4. Only general information on the complete size of all tiles and the framerate is provided here, which can be seen in detail in the Listing 4.3. There, the general information about the complete video size, the framerate, as well as the initialization track is provided, which is needed to reassemble the tiles into one video.

Each tile can then be found in additional AdaptationSets with the bitrate qualities defined from the command above separated in different Representation blocks, which leads to bandwidths of 5000Kbps or 250Kbps per tile, since we have split the 3840×1920 pixels into four 1920×960 tiles. Those individual Representation blocks are encoded in `hvt1` and correspond to the `hvc2` encoded base track. So, the two different Representation blocks can simply be switched without any further effort as the whole linkage to the base-track stays the same and only the bandwidth and id changes. The Spatial Relation Description for one tile track is shown in the Listing 4.4.

With that finished on the server side, the only thing left is how the content is delivered to the client, so it can decide on the best bitrate of each tile to get the most efficient live video with the information provided in the MPD file.

4.2.4 Content Delivery

To make the content available to others, some kind of content delivery system needs to be established. For that we decided to use the Nginx open-source Web server, which can act as a file server as well. Another benefit of using this server is that if we want to extend the content delivery to a larger network, it also includes a load balancer and reverse proxy.

Now, to access the data created by the GPAC DASH process, Nginx is configured to provide the files located at `/var/www/html/` on port 80 to the network, which can then

```

1 <AdaptationSet segmentAlignment="true" maxWidth="1920" maxHeight="960"
2   maxFrameRate="25" par="2:1" bitstreamSwitching="true"
3   mimeType="video/mp4" startWithSAP="1">
4   <SupplementalProperty schemeIdUri="urn:mpeg:dash:srd:2014"
5     value="1,1920,0,1920,960"/>
6   <SegmentTemplate initialization="video1_dash_track1_init.mp4"/>
7   <Representation id="5" codecs="hvt1.1.6.L186.80" width="1920"
8     height="960" frameRate="25" sar="1:1" bandwidth="5007500"
9     dependencyId="2">
10    <SegmentTemplate media="video1_tile2_dash_track3_${Number}_rep1.m4s"
11      timescale="1000" presentationTimeOffset="599400"
12      startNumber="1" duration="1000"/>
13  </Representation>
14  <Representation id="9" codecs="hvt1.1.6.L186.80" width="1920"
15    height="960" frameRate="25" sar="1:1" bandwidth="257500"
16    dependencyId="2">
17    <SegmentTemplate media="video1_tile2_dash_track3_${Number}_rep2.m4s"
18      timescale="1000" presentationTimeOffset="599400"
19      startNumber="1" duration="1000"/>
20  </Representation>
21 </AdaptationSet>

```

Listing 4.4: MPD AdaptionSet of one tile segment, including SRD information as well as timing and bandwidth information for both tile qualities, which are needed for the tile selection process on the client side to download the correct tile.

be accessed via `http://Server_IP:80/`. To actually get access to the files stored in the `tmpfs`, a link must be created between `/tmp/dashlive` and `/var/www/html`. With that setup, everything is done so that the client can load the MPD file and the individual segments from the server at the URL `http://Server_IP:80/dashlive/`. To visualize the process so far, in Figure 4.3 the already finished parts of the previous illustration shown in Section 4.1 are highlighted.

4.3 Client-Side Implementation

Now that the server is ready and set up to provide a tiled H.265/HEVC stream via the DASH protocol, a client application that is capable of selecting the correct tiles, downloading them, recreating a full video and display it without any kind of stutter needs to be created. For that we decided to work on a Unity project build for Android-based devices, as most of the standalone VR-HMDs run an Android operating system, so the application can also be used on Android-based mobile phones.

As we initially thought that the video playback can be done completely with the tools provided by Unity, the realization of a seamless video playback is described in multiple

Figure 4.3: Visualization of the parts included in the finished implementation of the Server-side.

stages, where we first tried to create the application only with Unity, and then switch to a native video player and improved that step by step to be as efficient as possible and create an immersive experience with no interrupts for the client device.

4.3.1 Downloading and Parsing the DASH files

When starting the application, the MPD file is first downloaded from the server, as it contains all the information to correctly configure the video player. The document is then parsed to extract the timescale, duration, start number, and segment duration to identify the correct segment numbers later on. Followed by identifying and downloading the correct initialization file names for video and audio, as they do not change any more. Lastly, the tile layout and the amount of different tile qualities are extracted which are needed to initialize the tile selection process.

4.3.2 Tile Selection

The idea was to create a Unity scene with the camera in the middle of a sphere, where the sphere should represent the video screen for the 360° video. Then, by projecting the tiles onto the sphere, the currently visible tiles should be detected with the information of the camera rotation parameters. This concept can be seen in Figure 4.4.

For that, four different tile groups are differentiated, namely, fully visible tiles, partially visible tiles, surrounding tiles, and not visible tiles. This gives the possibility to fine-tune

Figure 4.4: Tile selection process on the Client-side.

the quality selection per tile, where in the optimal case, only the fully visible tiles are downloaded in the best quality, and the further away the tiles are, the lower the quality should get, so there is no sudden drop quality wise. This would of course require the server side to also provide four different quality levels. If there are less quality levels provided by the server, the tiles near the view port get the best quality.

Then only the correct segment number needs to be calculated, which is done with the timing information from the MPD file extracted previously. With that information, it is now possible to download all individual tiles and the appropriate audio segment to create the video segment.

4.3.3 Creation Of A Playable Video

Now the identified files are downloaded, where each download runs in a separate co-routine to be able to download them in parallel. When all files are there, the init file, which we already have from the parsing process, is concatenated with the tiles in left-to-right, top-to-bottom order. Separately, the audio file is also concatenated with its init file, which then gives us two concatenated files in total.

To get a playable video and audio format, these two files need to undergo the reversed process which is done on the server. For that we cross-compiled the GPAC library with the Kvazaar encoder embedded for Android arm64 devices. This was done with openjdk-8 and Androids Software Development Kit (SDK) 32 and Native Development Kit (NDK) 24 to be compatible with the current Android version running on the Meta Quest devices.

With this cross-compiled library, we create a native C++ Dynamic Link Library (DLL) which can take the concatenated video file and produce a playable file in the `mp4` format and also the concatenated audio file that produces a playable audio file in the `wav` format. This was done by creating an input filter that processes the concatenated file. The filter is then connected to the `tileagg` filter, which can take Kvazaar created tiles and combines them into a playable video, and finally a connection to a destination filter for the output. The way this looks like for the aggregation of the video file is shown in the Listing 4.5.

In Unity, we have to create the folder structure `Assets/Plugins/Android/` where the created `.so` file should be placed, as well as all library dependencies. To access this native library from Unity, the specific function must be imported with a `DllImport`, which is

```

1  extern "C" __attribute__((visibility("default")))
2      int runTileAggregator(const char* inputFilePath,
3                          const char* outputFilePath)
4  {
5      GF_Err gf_err = GF_OK;
6      GF_FilterSession* session=gf_fs_new_defaults(
7          (GF_FilterSessionFlags)(
8              GF_FS_FLAG_NO_REGULATION |
9              GF_FS_FLAG_NO_PROBE
10         ));
11
12     GF_Filter* src_filter = gf_fs_load_source(session,
13         inputFilePath, NULL, NULL, &gf_err);
14     GF_Filter* tileagg_filter = gf_fs_load_filter(session,
15         "tileagg", &gf_err);
16     GF_Filter* dst_filter = gf_fs_load_destination(session,
17         outputFilePath, NULL, NULL, &gf_err);
18
19     gf_filter_set_source(tileagg_filter, src_filter, NULL);
20     gf_filter_set_source(dst_filter, tileagg_filter, NULL);
21
22     gf_err = gf_fs_run(session);
23     gf_fs_del(session);
24
25     return gf_err;
26 }

```

Listing 4.5: Reduced version of the C++ Dll for Android, to reassemble the concatenated tiles into a playable video. The error handling is removed from this listing for better visibility.

shown in the Listing 4.6.

After calling the aggregation function for the video and audio file, we are ready to show the result on the client device.

4.3.4 Displaying The Video

As all the needed files are now present on the client device, the video player must be prepared to display the video file in mp4 format as well as the audio clip must be loaded. To do so, a video player game object is created in our scene which is attached to the previously mentioned sphere. To make sure that the video is displayed correctly later on, a shader was created which maps the individual pixels to the inside of the sphere. Then the prepare function is called, and we wait for it to return. For audio, an audio source is added to the camera game object, and the created audio file in wav format is set. When

```

1 public class GPACWrapper : MonoBehaviour
2 {
3     [DllImport("gpac_tileagg")]
4     private static extern int runTileAggregator(
5         string videoInputPath, string outputPath);
6     ...
7     private IEnumerator GenerateNextVideo(int index)
8     {
9         string catVideoPath = catVideoPaths[index];
10        string vidPath = videoPaths[index];
11        Task.Run(() =>
12        {
13            int result = runTileAggregator(catVideoPath, vidPath);
14        });
15    }
16 }

```

Listing 4.6: Reduced version of the Dll import in Unity and call of the native function to recreate a playable video out of the concatenated file.

the prepare function is finished, the application is ready to start the playback of both files so that the client can see and hear what is captured from the camera. Now, all individual parts are finished as illustrated in Figure 4.5.

4.3.5 Stage 1: Creating A Seamless Playback Experience

Now as all individual parts are there, seamless video playback must be ensured. In the individual steps explained above, all of them run sequentially, which can of course not create a seamless experience, as the whole download and preparation process takes its time. So to pass this problem, a second video player, as well as a second sphere, were introduced in the scene to be able to alternate between them. With them set up, when starting the application, the MPD file is first downloaded and parsed. Followed by the first video player that starts to calculate the visible tiles, downloads and concatenates them, and prepares the video player until it is ready to play. When starting the playback, the second video player starts with its process, again downloading and preparing the following segments, but when the preparation is finished, it does not automatically start the playback, it waits until the already running player is finished.

After the first video player has finished its segment, the associated sphere is disabled, and the sphere of the second video player is activated, the new audio file is loaded, and the playback of the second player starts. The first player then starts the process of retrieving and preparing again. With this procedure, it is possible to create a seamless transition between the individual DASH segments produced by the server, resulting in a delay that is approximately three times as large as the segment length defined by the server.

Figure 4.5: Overview of the individual parts managed by the Client-side implementation.

Reducing the segment length enabled near real-time video transmission, but also revealed limitations of the Unity video player. The preparation phase required up to three seconds, leading to a minimum segment time of around four seconds, as downloading and reassembling the files required additional 300 milliseconds. This constraint not only led to delays of roughly ten seconds, but also caused noticeable degradation when changing the viewport, as a high quality image at the current viewport is only created after the completion of the current and following segment.

4.3.6 Stage 2: Improve Seamless Playback With Native Video Players

The initial setup enabled a working prototype, but to get closer to real-time streaming, further optimizations were required. Therefore, we decided to create our own video player as there is no way to tweak the performance of the Unity built-in player. For that we used the Android Media library, which gives the possibility to directly decode the video frame by frame on hardware encoders, as the current generation has H.265/HEVC included. We created another C++ DLL which is called from a C# bridge, responsible for the communication between Unity and the DLL.

The video player gets initialized with a texture created by Unity, which is attached to the sphere, together with the size parameters and the current video path. Then the Android Media library opens the video file and loads it into one of the hardware decoders to decode the first frame. This produces an image in the YUV format as the output, which

cannot be directly displayed by Unity's texture. To address this problem, the YUV image needs to be converted to the RGBA format that can be displayed, resulting in extensive calculations on the CPU. When the first frame is converted, a message is sent back to Unity that the preparation is finished. This allows the call to perform the texture update, which needs to be triggered by Unity's render thread, to write the data onto the texture. With that version, it is possible to achieve a preparation time of less than one second, as loading the first frame is still a time-consuming task, but so we are able to reduce the segment time by half compared to our first approach.

However, the conversion from YUV to RGBA remained a bottleneck. Even with a parallelized optimize approach, the process required 25 to 35 milliseconds per frame, which is enough to display a 24 Frames Per Second (FPS) video but inadequate for 30 FPS, where delays accumulate over time. To address this limitation, a frame drop mechanism was integrated into the decoding loop, which ensures that only frames that could be processed in time were displayed, while late frames were discarded.

This setup enabled a seamless stream with minimal delay and without noticeable frame drops during segment switches. By reducing the segment length to two seconds, the system achieved a total latency of approximately six to seven seconds between the camera capture and the video displayed at the client. To show the communication of the individual players in the implementation, Figure 4.6 illustrates the individual parts of the program with the time consumed at each step. It also represents the way in which the two players communicate with each other to have a seamless switch between them.

4.3.7 Stage 3: Optimize Playback Pipeline With SIMD

To maintain a stable framerate of 30 FPS on devices without dropping frames while processing the video, standard parallelization and loop unrolling proved insufficient. Therefore, `arm neon` instructions were used to convert YUV to RGBA using the Single Instruction, Multiple Data (SIMD) technique on devices that support it. This technique enabled the ability to process eight pixels at a time, allowing 4K video frames to be converted within 15 to 20 milliseconds and therefore avoiding frame drops.

Since the conversion speed is faster than the required display rate, an additional synchronization step was introduced. Instead of dropping frames, as in the earlier approach, the system now delays the output until the appropriate display time. In Figure 4.7, the process from the initialization of the application on the client, until ten seconds of video processed and displayed on the device, can be seen. Every function call on the client is listed, as well as the frames produced and displayed, which end up being 300 frames after ten seconds, showcasing that not a single frame is dropped.

What is interesting to see here is that the time consumption for the frame generation is still on the upper limit while the second video decoder is preparing. This is visualized by the color coding in the Framecount line, where green indicates that the frame was generated fast enough, and red took too long. As none of them took twice the time and

Figure 4.6: Representation of the client side workflow, including Unity and native libraries with timings from two video segments.

not many of them took too long after another, no frame was needed to be dropped.

In addition, a detailed view of the start of the first video segment is shown to visualize frame processing and what happens in the meantime on the second video player. What also can be seen here is that the main bottleneck is still the decoding of the first frame, which is part of the preparation process, as this limits us to reduce the segment time down to one second. Also, here the frame counter is shown in the individual parts, to showcase that 60 frames are processed and displayed within the two seconds of the first video.

With this implementation, a stable 4K 360° video stream, captured at 30 FPS from a camera, can be processed and displayed. It is tiled and converted into the DASH format on a server and downloaded, processed, and displayed on a client device with around six seconds of latency when using two-second segments.

(a) Ten second diagram of video stream showing the main function calls and their time consumption. Frame generation time is colored in red if it exceeded the expected frame time.

(b) Detailed view of frame generation and function calls. Frame generation time is colored in red if it exceeded the expected frame time.

Figure 4.7: Timing diagram of function calls with SIMD implementation and CPU YUV to RGBA conversion tested on Meta Quest 3.

```
1 void NV12ToRGBABuffer(uint8_t *yuv, uint8_t *rgba, int width, int height)
2 {
3     int frameSize = width * height;
4     for (int j = 0; j < height; j++)
5     {
6         uint8_t *rgba_ptr = rgba + j * width * 4;
7         uint8_t *y_ptr = yuv + j * width;
8         uint8_t *uv_ptr = yuv + frameSize + (j >> 1) * width;
9         for (int i = 0; i < width; i += 2)
10        {
11            uint8_t u = *uv_ptr++;
12            uint8_t v = *uv_ptr++;
13            *rgba_ptr++ = *y_ptr++;
14            *rgba_ptr++ = u;
15            *rgba_ptr++ = v;
16            *rgba_ptr++ = 255;
17            *rgba_ptr++ = *y_ptr++;
18            *rgba_ptr++ = u;
19            *rgba_ptr++ = v;
20            *rgba_ptr++ = 255;
21        }
22    }
23 }
```

Listing 4.7: Packing YUV data into an RGBA buffer, to be able to transfer the data to Unity's shader.

4.3.8 Final Stage: Optimizing CPU Load With Shader-Based Color Conversion.

The playback of 4K 360° videos at the desired frame rate of 30 FPS was achieved without the need for frame drop, although a small number of frames were occasionally generated too late. However, the last limitation was the inability to reduce the segmentation time to one second. Since color conversion was still performed on the CPU, even with optimized SIMD instructions, this task represented a computational bottleneck that could be achieved with much higher efficiency by the GPU.

To overcome this, the YUV data produced by the decoder was packed into an RGBA texture buffer, as Unity on Android devices only allows the creation of RGBA textures. This was accomplished by writing two pixels for every pair of Y values sharing the U and V components, and performing direct pointer assignments instead of the full per-pixel calculations on the native C++ side. The function implementing this mechanism is shown in the Listing 4.7.

With this change, even without optimizing it with SIMD instructions, it was possible

```
1  float3 YUVtoRGB(float y, float u, float v)
2  {
3      float c = 298 * ((y * 255.0) - 16);
4      float d = (u * 255.0) - 128.0;
5      float e = (v * 255.0) - 128.0;
6
7      float r = (c + 459 * e + 128) / 256.0;
8      float g = (c - 55 * d - 136 * e + 128) / 256.0;
9      float b = (c + 541 * d + 128) / 256.0;
10
11     return float3(r, g, b) / 255.0;
12 }
13
14 fixed4 frag(v2f i) : SV_Target
15 {
16     float3 norm_dir = normalize(i.direction);
17
18     float2 uv;
19     uv.x = 0.5 + atan2(norm_dir.x, norm_dir.z) / (2.0 * UNITY_PI);
20     uv.y = 0.5 - asin(norm_dir.y) / UNITY_PI;
21
22     float4 packed = tex2D(_MainTex, uv);
23     float3 rgb = YUVtoRGB(packed.r, packed.g, packed.b);
24     return float4(rgb, 1.0);
25 }
```

Listing 4.8: Shader implementation, to unpack the YUV data, transmitted over the RGBA buffer, transformed to be displayed inside a sphere and converted to correct values for Unity's RGBA texture.

to reduce the CPU processing time from 15 ~ 20 milliseconds when doing the complete conversion with SIMD, to 8 milliseconds, since just assigning pointers is much faster than doing the entire calculation on the CPU.

To display the packed data, a custom shader was implemented that unpacks the YUV values from the RGBA buffer and computes the final RGB values for each pixel of the texture. This process, including the access of each pixel, the transformation to the inside of the sphere, the loading of the corresponding YUV values from the texture buffer and the conversion of them into RGB values, is presented in the Listing 4.8.

With this implementation, the computational effort was shifted from the CPU to the GPU, allowing all frames to be produced in time, even while the second video player was preparing. The reduced CPU workload also lowered the computation time of all other function calls, as they were performed in parallel. A further optimization introduced a SIMD version of the YUV packaging, which reduced the packaging time to 3 milliseconds,

Figure 4.8: Comparison of function durations tested on the Meta Quest 3.

as well as the setup of the decoder and the decode process of the first frame, as illustrated in Figure 4.8.

This final client-side implementation enables the playback of a full 360° video recreated of a tiled DASH stream with 30 FPS, by utilizing the CPU for packaging the YUV data and using the GPU for the calculations of the pixel values. This allows a reduction of the segment time to one second, as the process starting from tile selection until the conversion of the first frame can be performed in under one second, which is presented in Figure 4.9.

Although the system can process one-second segments in time under controlled conditions, this configuration remains at the performance limit. In practice, it is still preferred to stay with two-second segments to ensure a seamless live streaming experience. Unfortunately, the reduction of CPU resources did not have a big impact on the Android Media library used to decode the first frame, which is still our most time-consuming step in the preparation phase.

4.4 Limitations

While this Chapter provides all the necessary steps to create a functional 360° live experience for high quality content delivery, there are also some limitations that must be considered. These limitations arise on both sides, the server implementations, which face problems in handling the data efficiently, as well as the client where limitations with re-assembling the downloaded files and efficiently decoding the produced video arise. Also,

Figure 4.9: Timing diagram of frame generation and function calls tested on the Meta Quest 3 with YUV packaging to an RGBA buffer utilizing SIMD instructions and converted on the GPU to accurate pixel values.

this implementation is restricted to 360° videos and cannot be generalized to other video formats.

4.4.1 Server-Side Tiling Limitations

The server-side implementation depends on external frameworks such as the GPAC multimedia framework with a combination of the Kvazaar encoder to be able to create the tiled stream. As the GPAC framework server efficiently acts as an rtmp server and DASH creator, the Kvazaar encoder used for tiling our video is only implemented utilizing the CPU. Although it would have been possible to tile the video by hand and encode it with FFmpeg and GPU support, it was not possible to create a video without noticeable borders on each tile.

This forced us to stay with the Kvazaar encoder, which limited us in the amount of tile qualities due to the heavy use of the CPU. With the available resources, it was not possible to create more than 3 tile qualities, even when only using 24 FPS and the lowest upload rate of 10Mb/s. Also creating an 8K video experience was not possible due to the heavy CPU usage. Another interesting limitation of Kvazaar is that the amount of tiles is limited to a maximum of 16 tiles per direction.

4.4.2 Client-Side Video Reassembling Limitations

As there is the problem with GPAC and Kvazaar on the server-side, it is also not optimal to use it on the client-side. However, there is no way to bypass those frameworks as the content which should be shown is also created with them. Due to the fact that we cannot get higher amounts of tiles from the server side, we do not face the problem of the limitation of the tile amount on the client. At least the client can handle as much as the server version.

Still another problem occurred in the native implementation for the tile aggregation, which is the need to use file I/O to pass the tiles to the GPAC filters, as well as creating only files as output. This limits us on the way we have to handle the downloaded data and how we pass them to the video player. Therefore, we had to create a file with the downloaded tiles, where all of them are concatenated in the correct order, pass this file to GPAC, and receive a playable file as output. This results in a total of four files for each video player, as the video and audio are separated. This is especially a problem, as writing and reading from and to the disk is a resource-intensive operation, which could be avoided if there is a memory-based way to feed the GPAC filters.

4.4.3 Client-Side Unity Limitations

What is also worth mentioning are the limitations on the Unity side, as we expected to be able to directly use their built-in tools to display the downloaded segments after each other, which ended up not being the case when using videos that only last a few seconds. As described in Section 4.3.5, the Unity built-in video player took up to three seconds to prepare the video before it can be played.

This forced us to create our own video player which reduces the preparation time so that we can work with video segments with a duration of one second. When implementing this, we came across another limitation from the Unity engine, which is the fact that they are only capable of providing textures in the formats of RGBA and different variations of it for Android. Even though they have one variation of YUV implemented, the YUY2 format, this is not what we get from our decoder and is also only supported for Windows and Xbox One, as stated in the Unity documentation [73]. So to display our native decoded video we have to convert the YUV data to RGBA on the native side, or circumvent this CPU heavy task and store the YUV data in an RGBA buffer, which still needs to be performed on the CPU, but the conversion is done by the GPU by a custom shader.

As described in Section 4.3.8, each YUV pair was packed into one RGBA buffer, where theoretically two YUV pairs could be transmitted in one buffer, as the U and V values are always used for two Y values and the alpha channel is always fixed to 255. So we tried to pack them in the order of Y Y U V in the RGBA buffer, but it was not possible to create a shader that was capable of recreating the correct image without any distortions. This forced us to still use the full RGBA buffer size, which means that we have to transmit the same data multiple times.

4.4.4 Client-Side Android Media Library Limitations

One of the biggest issues we detected when creating the client implementation was the time that a video player needed to be ready to show the first frame. With Unity's video player, there was no option to adjust the settings to speed it up, so we decided to create our own native version of a video player, where we thought that we can reach sub-second preparation times to display one-second video segments without a delay.

By implementing a video player with the Android Media library, where we can directly communicate with the decoder and manage the buffer queues by ourselves, we were able to reduce the time until the first frame is shown compared to the Unity video player. However, the time it takes for the decoder to get a valid output for the first frame is high, even when nothing else is running in the meantime. Also, preparing the decoder with as much information as possible did not influence the time needed, as we always get the same video format, framerate, image size, and overall video settings for each video segment we want to display. All we were able to do to reduce the time was try to optimize the workload as much as possible, which led to the result of about half a second for the load of the first frame.

Also, the fact that the decoding of the first frame is significantly faster on the Meta Quest 2 compared to the Meta Quest 3, which is the predecessor and has a slower CPU as well as GPU, but the same media format, did not help in finding an explainable solution to optimize this process.

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In this Chapter, the results will be evaluated, first looking at the setup used for the tests with a detailed view of their specifications, followed by an extensive test of the servers tiling and DASH creation configurations showing the resource usage for different scenarios. Then a video analysis between our implementation and a SotA version of H.265/HEVC DASH streaming will follow, where we examine the quality improvements which are possible. Lastly, the client download rate for different tile setups will be shown to find the best setup to reduce the network utilization to a minimum while still getting the best experience.

5.1 Test Setup

The tests were performed using a desktop PC with the specifications shown in Table 5.1 running the server application.

To capture 360 ° video content and transmit it to our server, we used a QooCam 8K Enterprise by Kandao [74], a professional 360 ° camera that can capture 8K videos at 30 FPS, perform real-time stitching and live streaming with H.264/AVC and H.265/HEVC

Component	Details
CPU	AMD Ryzen 7 5800X 8-Core Processor (3.8GHz with boost up to 4.7GHz)
Motherboard	ASUS Prime B450-PLUS
GPU	AMD Radeon RX 5700 XT (8GB GDDR6 VRAM)
RAM	32GB DDR4 3.200 MHz
Operating System	Linux Ubuntu 22.04.5 LTS, kernel 6.8.0-65-generic

Table 5.1: Test server setup specification.

encoding with up to 150 Mb/s. One big benefit is also that it has an RJ45 port, which allows for a much more stable network connection than WIFI.

As client devices, we used Meta Quest 3 as the primary HMD for immersive VR content testing, as it has a high-resolution display and is capable of SIMD instructions, which allowed us to test the differences in YUV to RGBA conversion. For further performance tests, we also used the predecessor, Meta Quest 2, to see the effect of different hardware specifications for our client implementation.

The Samsung A53 smartphone was used to measure network utilization, selected for easier FoV control to always reproduce the same scenery while performing multiple tests, as well as to show that the software runs on a mid-level Android device.

5.2 Video Transcoding Performance

In Figure 5.1 the first datarate test and CPU usage of the working tiled streaming can be seen, where we have an upload rate of approximately 20Mb/s and a download rate of around 4,5Mb/s. The setup explained before encodes a 4K video with 30 fps received with 20mb/s into two 8×4 tiled streams once with 20Mb/s and the second with 1Mb/s. The streams are saved in `tmp` memory and can be accessed through `nginx`, resulting in an overall CPU usage of around 70%. This was the main setup which was used for our test scenarios, with two second segments, as well as an intra frame every two seconds, a GOP length of 8, one reference frame, and a frame-level parallelism of 2.

The following evaluations were performed with the `htop` tool created by Hisham Muhammed [75] in 2004. As the interval between intraframe creation and segment duration does not influence the efficiency on the server, they are not shown in the Tables, and it is tested with the values from above.

Table 5.2 shows the different configurations of GOP and Frame Parallelism settings and their influence on the CPU and Memory usage. For this test, we used a fixed resolution of 3840×1920 , a framerate of 30 FPS, an upload rate of 20Mb/s, a tile layout of 8×4 and two tile qualities with 20Mb/s and 1Mb/s.

What can be seen there is that the GOP size has a big influence on the CPU and memory usage, where frame parallelism only has an influence on memory consumption. Therefore, we decided to stay with the configuration of a GOP size of eight and a parallelism of 2 for the further tests, as it was found to be the most efficient way.

(a) CPU and memory usage while tiling and DASH creation, displayed with htop.

(b) Comparison of upload and download with tiled streaming on the server displayed with iftop. 192.168.0.14 is the QooCam 8k as the streaming camera and 192.168.0.15 is the Meta Quest 3 used as the client device.

Figure 5.1: Usage statistics of the server while processing a 20mb/s 4K video.

GOP	Frame Parallelism	CPU (%)	Memory (%)
8	2	67	3.6
8	4	68	4.2
16	2	72	4.2
16	4	76	4.8

Table 5.2: Influence of GOP and Frame Parallelism settings on CPU and Memory usage. Tested with a resolution of 3840×1920 , a framerate of 30 FPS, an upload rate of 20Mb/s, a tile layout of 8×4 and two tile qualities with 20Mb/s and 1Mb/s.

Upload Rate (Mb/s)	FPS	Tile Qualities (Mb/s)	CPU (%)	Memory (%)
20	30	20, 1	67	3.6
20	30	20, 5, 1	100	4.9
20	24	20, 5, 1	82	4.5
40	24	40, 5, 1	95	4.9
40	24	40, 1	73	3.8
20	24	20, 1	62	3.7

Table 5.3: The effect of different tile qualities and different framerates on CPU and Memory usage. Tested with a resolution of 3840×1920 , a tile layout of 8×4 , a GOP size of 8 and Frame Parallelism of 2

To evaluate the effect of different tile qualities, upload rates, and framerates on CPU and memory workload, we did some tests with a fixed resolution of 3840×1920 which is shown in Table 5.3.

Interesting to see is that when encoding in more qualities the CPU usage rises very fast and the only way to achieve three different quality levels is by reducing the framerate to 24. What can also be seen is that changing the upload and tile quality from 20 to

Tile Layout	CPU (%)	Memory (%)
4x4	66	3.7
8x2	67	3.7
8x4	67	3.6
16x2	67	3.7
16x4	69	4.0

Table 5.4: The effect of different tile layouts on CPU and Memory usage. Tested with a resolution of 3840×1920 , a framerate of 30 FPS, an upload rate of 20Mb/s, a GOP size of 8, Frame Parallelism of 2 and two tile qualities with 20Mb/s and 1Mb/s.

Resolution	Rate (Mb/s)	Layout	FPS	Qualities (Mb/s)	CPU (%)	Memory (%)
3840x1920	20	8x4	30	20,1	67	3.6
3840x1920	20	8x2	30	20,1	67	3.7
3840x1920	20	8x4	24	20,1	62	3.7
7680x3840	20	8x4	24	20,1	100	12.5
7680x3840	10	8x2	24	10,1	100	11.4
7680x3840	10	8x4	24	10,1	100	11.5

Table 5.5: The effect of different resolutions on CPU and Memory usage. Tested with a GOP size of 8 and Frame Parallelism of 2

40 Mb/s only has a small influence on the CPU usage compared to adding another tile quality. What is also worth mentioning is that the difference in memory usage is not large in any of the tests and is always below 5%, which shows that this is not a limiting factor.

The test where the CPU usage was above 90 % sometimes started to lag behind, as there are also other services running on the server, as well as the one given with 100 % should only show that it was unable to execute in time to generate a live experience on the provided hardware.

To evaluate the effect of different tile layouts, we set up our server with a fixed resolution of 3840×1920 , a framerate of 30 FPS an upload rate of 20Mb/s and two tile qualities with 20Mb/s and 1Mb/s, where the results are represented in Table 5.4. Interesting to see is also the fact that a tiling setup with a multiple of cores available does not have much influence on the server resources. This allows us to always use a high tiling setup with up to 64 tiles without much difference from using 16 tiles.

As the last test to evaluate the server configurations, we used different resolutions as well as different upload rates, framerates, and tiling setups. There only the GOP size and Frame Parallelism remained the same as in the other tests. The results shown in Table 5.5 unfortunately show that our test server was not capable of tiling and creating the DASH format for 8K video in time, as even with the lowest upload rate possible on our camera and only two tile qualities, the CPU was locked at 100% which led to an always increasing delay in the video stream. Still, the memory usage received by `htop` and shown in the Table can be seen as realistic values, which shows an increase just a little bit smaller than expected, as it has four times the pixels to process.

5.3 Video Quality Comparison

As the download rate is approximately around 20% with the tiled version compared to the standard full 360° DASH streaming, it becomes possible to increase the bit rate on the camera and server side, resulting in four to five times better video quality for clients. Alternatively, the same data rate as non-tiled DASH streaming can be used to connect four to five times more clients to a single server.

In Figure 5.2, two versions of a 4K video are shown. In the upper image, the tiled video is created with 50Mb/s upload from the camera and then tiled into 8×4 tiles with 50Mb/s and 1Mb/s. This results in 1.57Mb/s high quality tiles for those inside the FoV and directly connected to them and 0.03Mb/s low quality tiles for tiles that are currently not seen. On the client side, this leads to an approximate download rate of 10Mb/s. The lower image shows a version where no tiling is done and the entire 360° video is created with 10Mb/s from the camera and then transferred via the DASH protocol to the client.

When comparing these two frames, the lower quality can especially be seen on borders, as they start to create a staircasing effect, which is shown in the zoomed in detail on the left. The overall noise is also much more present, as shown in the detailed view on the right.

5.4 Download Comparison

To show the advantage in regards to network traffic, Figure 5.3 shows the download rate for a 30 second video stream while also showing the actual rotation of the view and the amount of tiles which are loaded in full quality. In this case, it is tested with a 20Mb/s camera upload which is tiled into 8×4 tiles with 20Mb/s high quality and 1Mb/s low quality. The correlation between high quality tiles needed and the download rate is nicely visualized. It can be seen that the maximum download rate is at 12 Mb/s under heavy movement when downloading 20 tiles in the highest quality, which is mostly an edge case, as when looking at a 360 video, the POI does not suddenly change. This can also be seen in this graph, as it shows that in the average case, the download rate is between 6 and 8 Mb/s with 9 to 12 high quality tiles needed to be downloaded.

In Figure 5.3, above and below the graph, two frames of the tiled video are shown, where in the upper one, the HMD was looking at the center of the image and therefore 16 tiles needed to be downloaded in the highest quality, which are marked here with the red outlines resulting in a download rate of 10Mb/s. This frame refers to the start of the graph above. The frame below refers to the lowest amount of tiles shown in the graph, as well as the lowest download rate, where the HMD looked slightly up-left, resulting in only 9 tiles downloaded in high quality outlined in red.

As this only shows the situation of one tiling setup, the following Table 5.6 gives an overview of what tile settings are useful and what setup to avoid. The tests were performed with a 4K video send to the server with 20Mb/s upload from the camera. For the client,

(a) Tiled video with 50Mb/s upload and 10Mb/s download

(b) Full 360 video with 10Mb/s up- and download

Figure 5.2: Quality comparison of the tiled DASH 360° 4K video and non-tiled version with the same download rate per device.

we have four different tile visibilities, which are fully visible, partially visible, surrounding, and non-visible tiles that define the quality downloaded as described in Section 4.3.2. As client device, a Samsung A53 with an Android build was used, because it was not possible to get the same camera movement for the test with a HMD. For tracking network traffic, the `iftop` tool created by Paul Warren [76] in 2002 was used.

The Table also shows that a tile layout with only two tiles in one axis is not optimal, as no detailed selection can be done and most of the tiles are counted as partially visible tiles. This does not lead to a big problem when there are only two or three quality levels, but when the server is capable of producing all four quality levels, the highest quality

Figure 5.3: Download rate of tiled 20Mb/s video with example tiled video.

Server			Client		
FPS	Layout	Qualities (Mb/s)	Tile visibility	Tile Quality	Rate (Mb/s)
30	8x4	20, 1	2, 5, 5, 20	12, 20	7.0
24	8x4	20, 1	2, 5, 5, 20	12, 20	6.1
30	8x2	20, 1	0, 6, 0, 11	6, 10	6.9
24	8x2	20, 1	0, 6, 0, 11	6, 10	6.0
30	16x2	20, 1	0, 10, 0, 22	10, 22	5.3
24	16x2	20, 5, 1	0, 10, 0, 22	10, 22	4.5
30	16x4	20, 1	4, 7, 7, 46	18, 46	4.2
24	16x4	20, 1	4, 7, 7, 46	18, 46	3.5
24	16x4	20, 5, 1	4, 7, 7, 46	11, 7, 46	2.9

Table 5.6: Client download rates with different quality and tile configurations, a fixed resolution of 3840×1920 and an upload rate of 20Mb/s. The tile visibility indicates the number of fully visible, partial visible, surrounding and non visible tiles selected by the client, and the tile quality specifies how many tiles are selected at each quality level.

tiles would not be loaded. What is also shown there is that the more tiles there are, the better the tile selection can be made, and therefore the data rate can be minimized to its optimum.

5.5 Video Conversion Efficiency

One big topic in this thesis was the efficiency of displaying the created video on the client device. As shown in Section 4.3, we approached this in multiple different ways, as there was no straightforward way to implement this on Android devices with the tools provided by the Unity Engine. We created a native video player with the Android Media library, where we can directly communicate with the decoder, which outputs us a YUV image of every frame. This image needs to be converted into the RGBA color space to be displayable on Android devices.

In the first version, we converted the color space on the CPU with a parallel approach, which gave us a conversion time of approximately 30 ms on different devices. As shown in Figure 5.4a, which shows the time consumed by each function as well as the frames produced, we can see that we had to drop some frames, indicated in purple, as the Meta Quest 2 was unable to consistently create 30 frames per second in time. The abbreviations of the following figures, which show the function timings for different conversion techniques, are described in Table 5.7.

As we also had the Meta Quest 3 as a testing device, which is capable of arm-based SIMD instructions, we tried to optimize the conversion on the CPU for that device, so no frames need to be dropped any more. With that implementation, we were able to reduce the average conversion time to 18 ms, which allowed us to display a 4K video with 30 fps without the need of dropping some frames. However, some frames were generated too

(a) Function times tested with CPU color conversion. (b) Function times tested with CPU packaging and GPU conversion.

Figure 5.4: Timing diagram of function calls on a 4K video at 30 fps with different color conversion techniques, tested on Meta Quest 2. The color of the FCO indicates, whether the frame was generated in the correct time shown in green, red, if it was generated too late, and purple, if a frame needed to be dropped.

(a) Function times tested with CPU color conversion and SIMD instructions. (b) Function times tested with CPU packaging with SIMD instructions and GPU conversion.

Figure 5.5: Timing diagram of function calls on a 4K video at 30 fps with different color conversion techniques, tested on Meta Quest 3. The color of the FCO indicates, whether the frame was generated in the correct time shown in green, or red, if it was generated too late.

Abbreviation	Description
CVT	Time needed to calculate visible tiles and their layout
SVP	Start of video playback.
DAF	Time needed to download all files, including tiles and audio.
CWM	Time needed to create WAV and MP4 files ready to be played.
IDE	Time needed for the initialization of the Decoder.
DFF	Time needed for decoding the first frame of the video segment.
CFF	Time needed for the conversion from YUV to RGBA of the first frame.
FCO	Frame counter, visualizing the start and end of each displayed frame.

Table 5.7: Abbreviation description for timing diagrams of different conversion techniques.

late, which means that not all frames had the same display time, as shown in Figure 5.5a.

The interesting thing to see here is that the frames, which took too long, only occur, while the second video player was preparing and also needed some CPU resources. Also,

when comparing the time needed by the decoder for decoding the first frame as well as downloading the files, between the Meta Quest 2 and 3, it can be seen that the predecessor only needs a fraction of time. Overall, this results in a preparation time of around 0.6 seconds on the Meta Quest 2, compared to more than one second on the Meta Quest 3.

Since we were still unable to produce all frames in time, and the task of color conversion can be computed much faster on the GPU, we created a way to transfer the YUV data from the native library to the Unity shader. For this, the data was packed into an RGBA buffer by doing pointer assignments on the CPU, enabling the computational part to be performed on the GPU.

With that version, we were able to achieve an average conversion time of 8 ms on the Meta Quest 2, which completely removed the need of dropping frames, and also no frames were generated too late. This also allowed us to reduce the segment time to one second, as the preparation is also always completed in the available time, as seen in Figure 5.4b.

In the same way that we implemented the SIMD version for the Meta Quest 3 for the CPU, we also implemented a SIMD version for packaging on the CPU and conversion done by the shader on the GPU, as the frame generation time was significantly reduced in our previous approach. The SIMD implementation with shader side computation reduced the average frame generation time to 3 ms, which can be seen in Figure 5.5b at the conversion time of the first frame.

This version also improved our overall computation time for the second video player, when preparing the next video segment to approximately one second, which theoretically enables us to also use a segment length of one second. Still, it is at the upper limit do not create a delay, if one function call takes a bit longer than expected, therefore, to create a seamless playback experience on the Meta Quest 3, two second segments are still recommended. Interestingly, on the Meta Quest 2, were we able to process a one-second segment live stream without a delay caused by the preparation phase, as the decode process of the first frame is still faster there.

To provide an overview of the different color conversion techniques and their time consumption for frame conversion, as well as the time needed to decode the first frame, Table 5.8 was created. It includes results from the three test devices, as well as the four versions tested on the Meta Quest 3. Interestingly, the Meta Quest 2 outperforms the other devices no matter what conversion technique is used when looking at the decoder time for the first frame. In addition, even the Meta Quest 3 is only faster than the mid-range smartphone when fully utilizing the SIMD functionality combined with our YUV packaging method.

5.6 Video Transmission Latency

As this thesis is about real-time streaming, we also have to analyze the delay between recording the video on the camera, until it is displayed on the client device. There are multiple factors which influence this time, the biggest one is definitely the segment time, as

Testing Device	Method	Conversion Time (ms)	Decoder Time (ms)
Samsung A53	Conversion	31	673
Samsung A53	Pointer	12	651
Meta Quest 2	Conversion	27	182
Meta Quest 2	Pointer	8	195
Meta Quest 3	Conversion	25	689
Meta Quest 3	Pointer	8	745
Meta Quest 3	Conversion SIMD	18	791
Meta Quest 3	Pointer SIMD	3	564

Table 5.8: Average frame conversion times and Decoder times for processing the first frame of a segment after 120 frames of different conversion techniques, tested on Meta Quest 3, Meta Quest 2 and Samsung A53. Conversion stands for directly converting the YUV data to RGBA on the CPU, Pointer stands for packaging the YUV data to the RGBA buffer and conversion done on the GPU.

Tile Layout	Qualities (Mb/s)	Delay 1 (s)	Delay 2 (s)	Delay 4 (s)
8x4	20, 1	5.21	6.85	9.79
8x4	10	4.99	6.72	10.16
8x4	20, 5, 1	5.41	6.98	10.72
16x4	20, 1	5.45	7.07	9.84
4x2	20, 1	5.62	6.68	10.61

Table 5.9: Showing the Latency differences for one, two and four second segments under different server settings for tile creation, tested on the Meta Quest 2 with 24 FPS.

the earliest moment the server can provide the latest segment is after the defined segment time. In addition, the camera takes some time to process the image before it can be delivered over RTMP to the server. The server then needs additional time to process the stream into the different tiles and qualities, and finally, the client device needs to download the segment and process the data, to show it to the client. In Table 5.9, multiple different segment settings are shown, to see the difference to the current State-of-the-Art (SotA) version of low latency streaming as described in Section 2.7.5, where they reach latencies of under 3 seconds.

As shown in this Table, latencies that low could not be achieved, even when using only one-second segments, which resulted in delays of around five seconds. However, achieving the lowest possible latency was not the purpose of this thesis. It should be noted that different tile layout and quality settings did not significantly affect the delay. No clear pattern indicating which configuration produces the lowest latency was observed in the three different segment lengths. These variations can largely be explained by the start time of the application, as it was not possible to create an environment where the client starts at the exact same time as the newest segment was created.

The impact of segment length on latency is more apparent. An increase from one second to two second segments resulted in approximately 1.5 seconds higher latency, and

another 3.5 seconds when raising the segment duration to four seconds. This demonstrates that achieving a low segment time not only gives the user a more responsive experience, as the quality adjustment time of the viewport is directly linked to the segment time, but also gives the best real-time experience available with a tiled streaming approach.

5.7 Limitations

This Chapter showed what our created setup is capable of, what the most efficient settings are for different use cases, and where our hardware was not able to perform all tasks in the available time. Also, due to limited computational resources and hardware limitations, only a subset of desired scenarios could be evaluated, but what can be said overall is that the CPU usage of Kvazaar for the tiling was the most limiting factor on the server side, and the Android Media library restricted us on the client side.

5.7.1 Resolution Limitation

One big issue that came up while testing our implementation is that we were only able to perform tests with a resolution of 3840×1920 with usable results. On the one hand because CPU reached its limits when trying to increase the resolution to 7680×3840 , as shown in the Table 5.3, even with the lowest upload rate possible. On the other hand because the QooCam 8K, which we used as the camera, was only able to provide those two resolutions, no tests with smaller resolutions were possible to showcase the difference in resource usage. This is also the reason why we were unable to test other resolutions on the client device, and all tests were performed there with 3840×1920 .

5.7.2 Tiling Limitation

We were able to find that the change in the tiling layouts to a multiple of cores available on the CPU does not have a big influence on the usage and the higher the amount of tiles, the lower the download rate on the client, as shown in the Table 5.4. However, unfortunately, we were unable to perform tests with four qualities of tiles, which the client application is theoretically capable of, as we reached the CPU limits even with three quality levels at 30 FPS. Still tests with three quality levels were possible with 24 FPS, to show the benefit of multiple quality levels.

5.7.3 FPS Limitation

Another case that we were unable to test was the effect of different FPS settings, as our camera was only able to provide a stream with 24, 25 and 30 FPS, where our client devices are capable of displaying up to 120 FPS. It would have been interesting to see the utilization on the client devices with higher settings, but we were limited by the camera.

Another problem would also have been the CPU resources on the server, as it already reached its limits when running at 30 FPS and three tile qualities.

5.8 Use Cases

Using 360° cameras to deliver live content combined with the tiled DASH approach presented in this thesis can be used in a wide range of applications. By making use of the transmission of individual tiles, only the region of interest is streamed in high resolution, while areas in the periphery are delivered at lower quality. This approach enables multiple users to have the same high quality live experience while having a significantly reduced bandwidth requirement. Following, some use cases will be presented, which illustrate that our approach can provide a flexible and efficient way to deliver 360° live videos across different fields of application.

5.8.1 Sports and Music Events

Large scale live events such as football matches or music concerts, which take place in a fixed area observable from a single point of view, can be a good use case for live 360° video streaming. This would allow the end user to feel like being live in a stadium while the event takes place, and still have the possibility to decide where to concentrate at and explore the whole environment independently. Such flexibility is not possible in traditional broadcasts, which usually limits the viewers' perspective to the one chosen by the camera operator.

With the use of our tiled DASH streaming approach, it adapts the video quality to each individual viewer, allowing the best resolution in the current view while still having a low bandwidth requirement, as the surroundings are downloaded in lower qualities. This reduces the requirements for the client device, but especially for the streaming infrastructure. In large-scale events, where many end devices request data from the server, the server is relieved because only a fraction of the whole stream needs to be transmitted at the highest quality.

5.8.2 Education and Training

Another big topic can be the creation of an immersive learning environment for student or apprentice training with the use of 360° cameras to deliver realistic scenarios. Live streaming surgeries would, for example, allow the medical student to observe complex procedures in high quality when focusing on the surgeon's hands or the technical equipment necessary to monitor the patient in an operating room. By using our approach, the important parts the student is focusing on are always transferred in highest resolution, while relieving the network as the surroundings are transferred in lower quality.

A similar use case is, for example, the apprentice training in industrial fields when showing them the operation of heavy machinery or the work in unsafe environments.

They benefit from the ability to explore the entire environment as it is streamed in 360° which would not be the case when looking at traditional training videos. With our method, not only the bandwidth usage remains stable, the tile quality selection process can also be adjusted so that it improves the educational value by directing the attention to the relevant parts.

5.8.3 Tourism and Cultural Heritage

360° live videos can also be used for tours of museums, natural landmarks, or heritage sites, which would allow an audience around the world to access these cultural attractions, even if it is not possible to visit those places in person. With the tiled live streaming approach, users can explore the environment in detail as if they were directly there, while high-resolution imagery is created individually for the chosen point of interest. This approach balances immersion with efficiency, making such experiences available to a wider range of audiences by reducing the high bandwidth requirements.

5.8.4 Surveillance and Security

Another interesting sector could be the surveillance area when large areas need to be monitored. When modifying the quality selection process with automatic point-of-interest detection, the system can provide high-resolution imagery of suspicious activities or hot spots while providing lower quality for less critical areas. This would not only reduce the bandwidth requirements and the storage space needed for later analysis but would also allow security personnel to easier focus on the important parts of the video or find dangerous situations earlier.

5.8.5 Real Estate

The real estate industry is also a highly relevant domain for 360-degree live videos. Traditional property viewing requires significant time investment and physical presence for each interested client. This is often impractical, especially for international clients or in situations where the property does not provide the space to fit all applicants at once while still allowing them to see everything. Additionally, if there are mobility restrictions, this is a way to allow all clients to participate in the viewing.

With tiled streaming, these tours can be further optimized, as it enables the user to focus on specific areas of interest, transmitted in best quality, such as the kitchen, the balcony view, or the furniture, as every client has different interests, while less relevant areas are then transmitted in lower quality. In addition, it improves the marketing potential as it is easier to reach a global audience as a real estate agency.

Conclusion & Future Work

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This Chapter will conclude this thesis by giving an overview of what has been done and discussing future improvements for the software. At the beginning of this thesis, we were looking for a way to improve the State-of-the-Art H.265/HEVC video streaming, especially for the VR use case. Since the H.265/HEVC standard already works with tiles, we thought about a way to utilize this feature. In 360° video streaming, not all of the created video is seen by the end user, and because multiple users may focus on different regions, processing everything on the server was not feasible. This led us to the idea of using the DASH protocol, as it already has a quality selection feature.

The streaming of H.265/HEVC with DASH works by using the tile feature included in the standard, as it allows the video to split into independent streams. Using the GPAC multimedia framework, which is capable of producing a valid DASH session with individual tiles and the Kvazaar encoder, capable of splitting the incoming stream into multiple tiles with different encoding qualities, the baseline for the thesis was created.

For creating a fully functional setup, the missing part was now a client application, as there exist multiple video players, but none that is capable of displaying a H.265/HEVC video with independent tiles transferred with the DASH protocol. Therefore, we decided to create a Unity application for Android devices, as most modern ones already have a H.265/HEVC hardware decoder and also most of the VR devices run an Android operating system.

With the server set up and a basic Unity Android application created, we needed to add our individual tile set up so that we can have a benefit out of it. Therefore, we created our own libraries, capable of viewport prediction for multiple tiles, while creating the tile layout from the received MPD file of the server. The individual parts are then

downloaded and converted back to one H.265/HEVC file which can be decoded by the hardware decoder. As we wanted to get as close to real time as possible, while not sacrificing the quality the end user will see, we needed to build our own video player because the basic tools available from Unity were not capable to process everything in time. Therefore, we utilized the Android Media library by loading and decoding the video frame by frame and also created our own version of the YUV to RGBA conversion. For the last part, we even used the SIMD instructions available on some arm-based devices and a custom shader to create the best possible experience.

In the end, the created setup is capable of streaming high quality live 360° video to VR and smartphone Android devices, without loss of quality or significant latency increases. At the same time, the network traffic required from the client and server side is drastically reduced, allowing one to increase the download quality on the client side or increase the number of clients which can concurrently watch the stream from one server.

6.1 Discussion

With the final version, there are still some parts that do not run perfectly, as one of the main problems is the resource-intensive transcoding done on the server side, which limited our test cases to 4K. This can be of course bypassed by upgrading to a faster hardware when this should be used for production, but there are certainly ways to optimize it to run more efficiently on this hardware. However, to show that our plan to improve the State-of-the-Art DASH streaming worked, it was sufficient.

The second big topic that we encountered was the time needed to setup a decoder on Android devices. Even with the optimized version running a native library and directly accessing it instead of using the way Unity does it with their build-in video player, it is the most time consuming step on the client. However, it allowed us to create a seamless high quality 360° video stream. Further improvements are possible in this step, as well as in the process of color conversion. Although the current implementation performs well for the intended use case, this process should normally also be doable completely on the GPU, rather than packing everything on the CPU into an RGBA buffer, to transfer it to a shader for displaying at the texture.

As there is obviously still room for improvement, we were able to create a setup which can produce a high quality live stream to VR and mobile devices, allowing individual viewports for multiple users while drastically reducing the network requirements. This was achieved by increasing the time between the capture of the video by a camera until the presentation to the end user a little bit, which still is in the area of a few seconds. This shows that the concept works and that it is worth investing additional time and effort into it for further improvements.

6.2 Future Work

In this thesis the main objective was achieved, which was to show that it is possible to optimize the current State-of-the-Art for 360° H.265/HEVC live video delivery, but also, as already mentioned, there is still room for some improvements in different fields.

File I/O In the current version, we use GPAC together with Kvazaar on the client device to recreate a H.265/HEVC video. There we need to create a file that is a concatenation of the video initialization file with all individual tiles as input, and then we get a playable video file in the mp4 format as output. Diving deeper into the tiling mechanism of these libraries and enabling the possibility to directly pass the individual tiles via memory, as well as receiving a playable data stream, would remove the need to write two files for each DASH segment. This will lead to an increase in efficiency, as file I/O is a very costly process. Another benefit would be that, for further processing of the video, no file needs to be loaded again, as it is already stored in memory.

Decoder Initialization As extensively discussed, initializing the decoder is the part that takes the longest amount of time on the client side. By going deeper into the Android Media library, the initialization time could be reduced as all individual segments from the stream have the same properties. Therefore, the codec extraction should normally only be needed once at the start of the video stream, and not for each video segment.

Another approach can be, if the file I/O is removed, to directly feed the data stream to the decoder, which should also allow the decoder to continuously decode the video and remove the need of re-initialization after each segment.

Color Conversion Currently, the color conversion from the decoder output, which is in the YUV format, is converted to the RGBA format, which is needed by Unity's texture as there is no build-in texture which is capable of displaying the YUV format. To be able to transfer the YUV data to the Unity shader, which converts it into an RGBA image, we need to store the YUV image in an RGBA buffer performed on the CPU. Due to this process, the same data needs to be stored multiple times as the shader needs information per pixel basis. If it were possible to transfer the YUV data directly to Unity without the need to reorganize the data into an RGBA buffer, the entire conversion could be performed on the GPU. This would eliminate the need to move the image data from the GPU to the CPU and vice versa, which will significantly improve the performance on the client device.

Video Tiling On the server side, the time needed for tiling and DASH creation of the video should definitely be able to be reduced, since the complete process runs on the CPU without utilizing the GPU, which is made for tasks like that. Also, the need to completely transcode the incoming video in the same bitrate as it is received can maybe be removed. Currently, it is decoded and encoded again with the same bitrate, which is

a computationally intensive task. This would allow for higher quality streams, more tiles and also more different quality levels, to take full advantage of the tile selection on the client side.

Content Delivery As another approach not directly treated in this thesis, the setup of a wide CDN would be interesting, as this work was only tested in local environments and a simple content delivery server. This would allow for an efficient distribution of one live camera all over the world with low latency when there is a comprehensive implementation of content delivery with geo-aware routing, caching, and load balancing.

Point of Interest Prediction Lastly, POI prediction can be implemented so that the client always loads the tile that covers the POI in the highest quality. This would give the user an even more immersive experience, as when looking around the scenery, important parts are always detailed. With a good implementation, this would not increase the network requirements by much but would increase the immersion and quality of the user experience.

List of Acronyms

Glossary

3D-HEVC	3D High Efficiency Video Coding
aac	Advanced Audio Coding
CABAC	Context-Adaptive Binary Arithmetic Coding
CCITT	Comité Consultatif Internationale Télégraphique et Téléphonique
CDN	Content Delivery Network
CDNs	Content Delivery Networks
CGS	Coarse Granular Scalable
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CTU	Coding Tree Unit
CTUs	Coding Tree Units
DASH	Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP
DCT	Discrete Cosine Transform
DLL	Dynamic Link Library
DNS	Domain Name System
DPCM	Differential Pulse Code Modulation
FoV	Field Of View
FPS	Frames Per Second
GOP	Group of Pictures
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
H.264/AVC	Advanced Video Coding
H.265/HEVC	High Efficiency Video Coding
H.266/VVC	Versatile Video Coding
HDR	High Dynamic Range

HLS	HTTP Live Streaming
HMD	Head-Mounted Display
ISDN	Integrated Services Digital Network
ISO/IEC	International Organization for Standardization
ITU-R	International Telecommunication Union((Radiocommunication Sector))
ITU-T	International Telecommunication Union(Telecommunication Standardization Sector)
KNN	K-Nearest-Neighbors
LL-DASH	Low Latency DASH
LL-HLS	Low Latency HLS
LR	Linear Regression
MPD	Media Presentation Description
MV-HEVC	multi-view High Efficiency Video Coding
NALU	Network Abstraction Layer Unit
NDK	Native Development Kit
POI	Point of Interest
PPS	Picture Parameter Set
PTZ	Pan-Tilt-Zoom
QP	Quantization Parameter
ROI	Region Of Interest
RTMP	Real Time Messaging Protocol
RTSP	Real Time Streaming Protocol
SDK	Software Development Kit
SHVC	scalable High Efficiency Video Coding
SIMD	Single Instruction, Multiple Data
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SotA	State-of-the-Art
SPS	Sequence Parameter Set
SRD	Spatial Relation Description
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
tmpfs	Temporary File System
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
VOD	Video On Demand
VPS	Video Parameter Set
VR	Virtual-Reality
WPP	Wavefront Parallel Processing

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